

**Title: The Prospect and Challenge of Establishing Stock
Market in Ethiopia**

By

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Acronyms

NBE:	National Bank of Ethiopia
AABE:	Accounting and Audit Board of Ethiopia
AACC:	Addis Ababa Chamber of Commerce
RSC:	Rwanda Stock Exchange
GDP:	Gross Domestic Product
SOEs:	State Owned Enterprises
MOFEC:	Ministry of Finance and Economic Cooperation
GoE:	Government of Ethiopia
ECX:	Ethiopian Commodity Exchange
SEC:	Securities and Exchange Commission

Abstract

This study intended to assess the challenges and prospects to establish stock market in Ethiopia. Stock market is highly complex as one form of capital market. A well functioning stock market plays an important role not only for the development of financial sector but also contributes for economic advancement of any nation. In light of this, the study tries to explore three major determinant factors such as institutional, macroeconomic and policy aspects required to establish stock market in Ethiopia. The study employed mixed approaches that include in-depth review of literature, government policies and strategies, collection of relevant primary data, key informant interview with strategically positioned senior officials in different organizations in regards to stock market establishment. As the findings indicate, except for strong dream by the Government, there is weak institutional and policy arrangement to initiate, stimulate establishment of strong and functional stock markets in Ethiopia. Thus, the study concludes that policy maker should carefully consider regarding: Institutional factors: legal proclamations and trade law, setting up of public authority responsible to control the stock market, development professional and issue of financial intermediaries, education and awareness, private sector development, market infrastructure and issues of corporate governance which is still underdeveloped. Regarding macro-economic factors, given substantive economic progresses registered over the past two decades, Ethiopia has highly promising economic environment to establish and operate stock market. To encourage participation private sector, an important monetary and fiscal policy components such as taxation and interest rate policies should be considered in order to move faster establishment.

Key terms: stock market,

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Introduction

Ethiopia does not have a stock market except for commodities exchange which is allowing for few agricultural products. As one of most recent reform agenda, the current government announced to sell mega public enterprises such as Ethiopian Airlines, Ethio-telecom, Ethiopian Electric Power and others which are owned by the government. Following this reform idea there is the central question of how these mega public enterprises transfer to private sector. There is no transparent and clear platform to allow people and companies to invest and buy shares of these public enterprises. There are financial and non-financial institutes who have shares but there is no central place of exchange that is an important arrangement required to be in place to initiate stock exchange.

According to National Bank of Ethiopia monetary policy framework (2009), Monetary policy committee's code of conduct stated out that to promote financial sector development the committee expected to propose specific financial sector reform measures including restructuring of existing state owned banks, introducing stock market, venture capital, modern payment systems, other security markets (both primary and secondary), lease finance (NBE, 2009, P.11).

Different scholars define stock markets based on their own view. A contemporary literature suggests that stock markets provide services that boost economic growth and contribute to the achievement of national goals. According to Ruecker (2011) research work financial market is a place in which financial assets are created or transferred that it is channeling money from those who do put for immediate use from who do have. A place stocks, shares and bonds of all types are bought and sold (Gomez, 2013) and one way of efficient financial movement. Among the global stock market London and New York stock markets are oldest and well organized in the world. As depicted by (Edosa, 2014) provides facilities for stock brokers, investors and corporations to trade in stocks. Instruments such as bonds, stocks, commodities, derivatives, options, currencies and so

on are traded (Mishkim and Eakins, 2006). It is a part of global economy.

Many people (especially the poor) a chance to buy shares of listed companies and become part-owners of profitable enterprises. Allow sharing the profits of businesses to many people and helps to reduce large income inequalities (Kannan and Ijigu, 2013). Worku (2017) provides an overview that stock market is effective in rising capital, investment opportunity for individuals and institutions. Many scholars and researchers indicated that if countries establish a well-functioning securities market, it will provide substantial benefits for economic developments and to decrease monopoly.

Levine and Zervos (1996) conducted an empirical study and found out that there is a strong positive correlation between stock market development and long-term economic growth. Not only benefits to developed countries but also economy of least developing in a number of ways. A study which is done by Tesemma (2003) provided an overview that introducing stock market, allows de-concentration of ownership, improve accounting and auditing standards, provide effective tools for monetary and fiscal policy and help privatization efforts. Stock market generally used as economic policy instruments for financial management. Stock market improved regulation, privatization of state assets and the growth of institutional investors (Carmicheal and Pomerleano, 2002). Beside, improve allocation of resource as well as better management of risks.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Ethiopia is one of fastest growing economies in the world. However, the economy has been under state control through a series of development plans ever since the Imperial government that private sector role and contribution remained minimal. According to Ruecker(2011) assessment even though a significant development step has been taken by the Government since 1991, Ethiopia's financial sector is relatively small, closed and much less developed than those of other African countries. Poor financial infrastructure and less inclusiveness are cited as major impediments of the sector. The government dominates lending, interest rates, exchange rate and the largest banks and enterprises.

Many of African countries including Ethiopia their expenditure fund which is

available from external source either through loan and debts. Further, the development of securities markets contributes to economic development through the mobilization of savings and their channeling to the most productive enterprises (Tessema, 2003).

Although the formal Ethiopian state structure has been transformed from a highly centralized system to decentralized one, a number of challenges and problems are still remaining(Rucker,2011). The growth of corporation has a sound contribution to economic development through the participation of private sector. However, as depicted by Girma(n.d.) without an active and efficient security market , corporation will have only a modest impact.

According to National Bank of Ethiopia report (2018) there are nineteen banks (including commercial bank of Ethiopia) and more shareholders, seventeen insurance. Further, there are non-financial, many private companies and a few corporations who have been selling shares. But there is no legal market which is systematic, legalized and organized for share trading and re-trading implying that there is high share illiquidity.

With total assets of 46 percent of GDP, Ethiopia's financial system is shallow and does not serve well the needs of a transforming economy. Access to finance is identified as the main obstacle to business by 40 percent of firms (World Bank, 2015). Credit to the private sector was at a low 12 percent of GDP in 2017. The two state-owned banks, Commercial Bank of Ethiopia (CBE) and Development Bank of Ethiopia (DBE), represent 63 and 6 percent of total banking assets respectively serve as a key source of finance for infrastructure investments, SOEs and developmental projects. The resulting asset liability mismatch and a high portfolio concentration in specific sectors and enterprises create risks in the system and limits financing to private sector firms (World Bank, 2018).

According to Ministry of Finance and Cooperation domestic saving is insufficient to finance its ever increasing investment need. Moreover, foreign exchange earnings from export of goods and services finance a small portion of the country's imports. This calls for the need to finance the current account gap from capital flows. The country's total

public debt including central government, government guaranteed and public enterprises borrowing increased from USD 2.3 billion in 2006/07 to USD 23.5 billion in June(MOFED,2018).

Ethiopian investment sector tends to rely heavily on the banking. Accordingly, examine contributed for financial shortage. Besides, financial shortage is one of a main challenge for Ethiopian Small and Micro Enterprises. They have only met about 50% of the demand for their financial need (Girma, 2015). Through stock market and the corporate sectors are source of long maturing funds with relatively competitive prices. Accordingly, can generate finance for innovative, new and riskier business ideas and initiatives at a relatively low cost (Bekele, 2018).

Decision to establish stock market is in the power of the Ethiopian government and fill the existing financing gap of public and private companies by offering them an alternative financing route via the stock market. The study seeks to investigate and forward challenges and prospects of the establishment stock market in Ethiopia, by taking under the estimation of the intended economic reform.

1.3. Research Questions

Based on the above statements of the problem this research attempts to address the following questions.

1. Why is stock market not yet established in Ethiopian and what are challenges still exist?
2. Are the current economic structure and level of development sufficient to initiate a functioning stock market?
3. What are the prospects for the establishment strong and well-functioning stock market in Ethiopia in the near future?

1.4. Objective of the study

1.4.1.General objective

The general objective of this study is to explore the challenge and prospects of establishing stock exchange market in Ethiopian. This includes identifying the current economic particulars and government capacity to establish and operate the entity.

1.4.2.Specific objective

In order to achieve the above general objective of the study the following specific objectives addressed:

- To identify the binding factors which has been constraining the establishment of stock market in Ethiopia
- To identify whether the current economic structure and level of development are sufficient to functioning stock market
- To explore the prospect for the establishment of a stock market in Ethiopia in the near future

1.5.Scope of the study

Stock market issue is complex and multi-faced. There is no monotonic factor or indicator to depict all aspects. There are various determinants that related with the term. However, this research focused on three basic key determinants factors: institutional, macroeconomic and policy. Accordingly, Institutional factor mater to arrange during institutional reforms to promote financial sector development. Macroeconomic factors which appropriate with economic structure, economic size and level of development. Beside, monitory and fiscal policy issues assessed.

1.6.Significance of the Study

Stock exchange market refers economic and market policies. It defines as market place which is organized to purchase and sale of securities. However, mandatorily requires policy and legal aspect. There are two basic arguments concerning the establishment of stock market in Ethiopia which is for and against. The objective of the study is not to

support or against the establishment. However, to endeavor what looks the current status of key determinant factors regarding institutional, macroeconomic and policy factors.

This research is believed to have an important contribution to adding value on existing knowledge on stock exchange in Ethiopia in different perspective. In one side to investigate challenges still exists in the development of stock market in Ethiopia in terms of different point of view. Endeavor legal, institutional, economic structure and level of development.

1.6.1 Future researchers

The study would serve as an input for other studies, which may focus on similar topics and issues, to other researches, academicians, consultants and some professional associations to provide as an important in sight who conduct further researches on related fields as a reference material.

1.6.2 Actors of Stock market

Consequently, Ethiopian financial sector is poor and under developed. Stock exchange is one ways of which contribute to the development of financial sector. Banks, insurance, small and micro enterprises, public enterprises, and institutional investors, private companies, professional associations and organizations are the main actors of stock market. The study helps the government and those actors to trigger policy issues on stock market establishment to develop the financial sector.

1.6.3 Policy makers

The finding of the study might be used by policy makers as a road map for policy, strategy makers and implementers for in case of future implementation.

1.6.4. National Bank of Ethiopia

Furthermore, National Bank of Ethiopia is one of the pioneer actors under the development of financial sectors including stock market. The study may also be helping the Bank to take as additional support in the process of their study regarding the market.

1.7. limitation of the study

To know the experience of other country, the external sources (outside Ethiopia), required cost and time, this may make it not accurate. Only secondary data applied. Beside, on this researcher the experience of Rwanda intensively employed. However Rwanda stock market is relatively new and poor in terms of availability of relevant research and publication.

1.7.1. On the Concept of title

Issue of stock market is multifaceted. It requires rigorous research, cost and time. However, out of which institutional, macroeconomics and policy factors only a few of them are assessed.

1.7.2. Methodology Part

Research methodology employed based on mixed approach which is more relevant with mixed method of Creswell (2014) side by side approach. Accordingly, using this method has some potential threat in the validity. Out of which it may yield incompatible and difficult to merge findings.

1.8. Ethical consideration

The interview was conducted by letting the key informants have information about the purpose of the study and the type of information needed from them. Thus, it carried out after consent from the interviewees and at a place of their choice. They also informed that their names or any other potentially identifying information is not used to in the final report. Besides, they assured them that their responses will be kept confidential and results focus on the content of the discussion rather than identifying who said what.

1.9. Organization of the Study

The study has five chapters. The first chapter deals with introductory issues include background of the study, statement of the problem; objectives of the study and scope of the study are presented and so on. Theoretical and empirical literatures discussed in the second chapter. Chapter three provides some clue about the methodology and model specification used in this study. Chapter four present the results of the empirical analysis and interpretation of the findings. Conclusions and policy recommendations are provided in chapter five.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2. Introduction

Stock exchange market is a place which allowing for maximum effective competition among buyers and sellers. The fact of having an integrated market mechanism to bring together the many buyers and sellers at any point in time effectively results in the greatest way of trading.

In many study and available data suggests that an efficient stock exchange market has an important role for economic development policy. However, in Ethiopia the establishment is subject of debate to policy makers, private and public sectors. This paper seeks to focus on challenge and prospect of development of stock exchange market in Ethiopia. This chapter presents a summary of the review of the literature. The first part presents the review of the theoretical literature. The second summarizes relevant empirical evidence of stock exchange market. The third section presents the conceptual model.

2.1. Theory of stock market

The history of capital market tracks back to the 17th century has been operating in various forms. During Industrial Revolution in Europe capital market played essential roll by providing capital for new ventures. Especially stock market was originally started from 1883 in the continent of Europe and in Alexandria the innovative exchange in the Mediterranean (Jaleta, 2014). Max Weber suggests the idea of the stock market as a dynamic institution. The German sociologist defended the stock market against the conservative sectors those opposed to the commercialization and against socialists that took as symbol of capitalist iniquity. Weber argued that pure speculative commerce is helpful for private community and as important functions in price leveling but limited with regulation. By 1773 the first stock exchange, the London Stock Exchange was found (Vincent and Musomera, 2008). The New York Stock Exchange (National Association of Security Dealers Automated Quotation (NASDAQ), London Stock Exchange and the Hong Kong Stock Exchange are most popular. Levine and Zervos (1996) depicted stock market create incentives to invest with earn higher returns than more such as bank savings deposits that enhancing economic growth and development.

“Stock market is a security that represents a share of ownership in a corporation” (Mishkin and Eakins, 2006,p.4). Further, efficient markets theories shows that stocks are always in equilibrium and impossible for an investor to consistently beat the market. Fairly priced, reflect all publicly available information on each stock affect monopoly and prevent market failure.

Capital markets may be classified as primary markets and secondary markets. In primary markets, new bond or stock issues are sold to investors via the mechanism known as underwriting. On the other hand existing securities are sold and bought among investors or traders, usually on a stock exchange in the secondary markets (Gomez, 2013). Accordingly, through which a person who wants to save can directly supply funds to a person who wants to borrow. One form of financial liberalization in fostering financial development may increase long-run economic growth (Worku, 2017). Al-Wassal (2013) finds the primary function of stock markets is to serve as a mechanism for transforming savings into financing for the real sector

According to Ruecker(2011) stock market promote private sector development, enhance competition among banks, improves corporate governance, rewards sound economic policies and creates tools to conduct monetary policy. Recently, World Federation of Exchange and UNCTAD (2017) research report provides an overview of some of the ways in which stock exchanges contribute to economic growth and sustainable development. It focused on two main roles of exchanges: mobilizing resources to facilitate sustainable economic growth and development; and promoting good governance.

Financial market increases diplomatic relations to integrate trade, foreign direct investment, and technology transfer, developing the most capable professional, regulatory, well-informed consumers and investors’ relationships. Besides, promoting international accounting standards, corporate governance, good governance, transparency and accountability among all (Tessema, 2003). Kannan and Ejigu(2013) and El-Walassal(2013) identifies the advantages of stock market is to enhanced saving mobilization and risk management, offering liquidity to investments, redistribution of

wealth facilitated by diffused ownership, improved corporate governance, efficient resource allocation, vibrant financial system and as a barometer of the economy. Beside, providing many people a chance to buy shares of listed companies and as a result reduce income inequalities (Musonera, 2008) and increase remittances especially for (Legesse,2012).

As depicted in research work UNCTAD (2015) stock market create: Investment horizons: by providing ability to saving mobilizations as means of exiting investment, Transparency: helps to address information symmetry and through the initial listings; Investor protection: by rules of the exchange, combined with relevant securities market regulation, Pooling funds: by bringing together a large and diverse set of investors. For Small and Micro Enterprises by listing, create competition among Banks, increase volume of remittances, improves corporate governance.

Stock markets play a vital role in every economy. It serves to increase the national savings rate by creating incentives to invest, resource allocation, promotes efficient financial system, and allows wider participation in enterprise management and for a wider distribution of corporate profits(Tessema,2003). Stock market improves accounting and auditing standards, play a key role in providing the conditions necessary for innovations in technology and economic organization to occur (Chami, Fullenkamp and Sharma, 2009).A stock market encourages new business ideas to mushroom, creativity and innovation to flourish and help market efficiencies to improve. Any novel business idea that matures through time is presented in the form of initial public offering (IPO). “There are two things any secondary market must do: determinant a fair price for the security in (trade price discovery) and enable transaction to be made at this price quickly and easily (the provision of liquidity)” (Kohn, 2003, P.320)

2.1.1. Key Determinants Factors to Establish Stock market

Before establishing finical market the following practical questions must asked by policymakers: financial instruments, how introduce, types of markets and related institutions. Beside, borrowers, lenders, liquidity providers, and regulators are key players whose actions determine whether and how markets develop, to play crucial roles

in the proper functioning of financial markets (Chami, R.et.al, 2009). According to Steil,(2001) a blue print in developing modern securities trading infrastructure corporate and governance, privatization program, functional regulation and competition, encouraging foreign participation, technological infrastructure and public investment are needed as cited by (Yartey, 2007).

Financial market development is a by-product of economic expansion, which creates wealth and opportunities to develop the financial system (Chami, al.et 2009 and El-Wassal2013) there are two basic factors which affect stock market development: macroeconomic and institutional issue: Macroeconomic includes level of inflation and capital flows, income saving rate, (Yartey and Charles A., 2007and Tssema(2003) to develop financial market policymakers need to provide the necessary conditions including macroeconomic stability, per capital income and sufficient demand and supply.

I. Institutional Factors

A term institution which is defined by the research work Ei-Wassal(2013) refers either to the set of rules and norms that shape the social, political, and economic interactions among the members of society. To increase confidence, trust, protection to property right, less corruption and more transparency. Legal framework and institutional environment are important in protecting both the interests of companies and investors (Tessema, 2003). Borrower-lender compromise makes it easy to see why issues such as transparency and governance of institutions are important. To makes wider dissemination of information, in implementation of robust electronic trading systems, and the adoption of central depository system (Yartey and Adjasi, 2007).

1. Regulatory and legal framework

Regulation and legal framework play a supplementary role in stock market development. According to Edosa(2014) and Yartey and Charles A., (2007) and El Wassal,(2013)research work consumer and property rights protection, contract enforcement laws and corporate governance, to create deep and vibrant businesses environment requires strong institution and legal framework. Laws are often intended to prevent fraud and market

manipulation in the case of a dispute. A regulatory body plays an active role essentially when the conditions necessary for trading certain contracts and to provide coordination and direction for market development. There are commercial courts that specialize in hearing commercial cases, an independent judiciary works free from the interference of the political forces through proper enforcement of law (Legesse, 2012).

Key factors affecting the growth of security market is regulatory standards and institution as well as market infrastructure (Carmichael and Pomereano, 2002). Further, stock market investment installing better regulatory of trading infrastructure providing a safety net for investors and promotes market growth. On the supply side, privatization of state owned assets and public underwritings of closely held assets lead to the offering of new securities, while the growth of institutional investors: pension fund creates demand for new investment. “To some the regulation of security is merely an extension of fraud laws and customer protection to the particular circumstance of the security market”(Kohn, 2003,p-638).

2. Public Sector/ Regulatory body/

Beside, sound legal and regulatory framework, private sector credit evaluation capabilities, and public sector regulatory oversight needed. key features of the rule of law in financial markets includes both political and legal guarantees of civil liberties and property rights, the rule of law ,citizens can plan their future courses of action. According to LaPorta, Lopez-de-Silanes, Schliefer and Vishny (1997) the quality of institutions particularly with respect to the investor protection they afford, are useful in explaining cross-country differences in financial market development as cited by (Chami, al.et 2009). Large number of countries established and strengthening independent commissions to regulate capital markets. A notable thrust of this effort was the formulation of revised laws and regulations (Miskhin and Eakins, 2006).

3. Market Infrastructures

There are various types of infrastructure that governments need to build. These would

include the following elements: a modern payment system for clearing and settling securities transactions, retail payments and large value payments as well as a physical infrastructure for the operation of primary and secondary markets. Particularly, both supply and demand for shares should be sufficiently large: a larger number of buyers and sellers, stock market regulations and rules must be conducive to trading (Chami et al., 2009), can be differentiated by their trading systems in terms of transactions handled, types of transactions, types of information available to market participants. Dealers and brokers (Intermediaries), trading system and credit-rating agencies are the most important system elements in market infrastructure (El-Wssal, 2013).

4. Banking Sector Development

The development of the banking sector has a significant impact on the development of stock market. According to Yartey and Charles A. (2007) well developed banking sector is necessary preconditions for the efficient functioning of stock markets especially at the early stages. A progressive and sound banking system is required to quicken the development of the financial market (Kazarwa, 2015). Security firms are allowed to make loans, offer credit and debit cards and providing ATM accesses. In addition security firms could sell some types of insurance. It is not hard to understand why bankers were frustrated; regulation prevented them from competing with securities firms, but no low restricted security firms from competing with banks (Mishkim and Eakins, 2006).

5. Corporate Governance

Corporate governance' refers to the overall legal, institutional and regulatory framework in which the interests of stakeholders surrounding companies are coordinated and protected (Fekadu, 2010) as cited by (Legesse, 2012). The quality of the corporate governance determines the confidence and willingness of investors to participate in investment and financial markets. Further, structure, rules and institutions that determine the extent to which managers act in the best interest of shareholders Claessens et al, (2007) as cited by El-Wassal,(2013), strong corporate governance and financial transparency are critical for the development of stock markets to enhance investor confidence and increase equity investment. Principle of Organization for Economic

Cooperation and Development (OECD) incorporate corporate governance process: The right of shareholders, the equitable treatment of shareholders, the role of stakeholders in corporate governance, disclosures and transparency and the responsibility of the board (Carmichael and Pomereano, 2002).

6. Political Stability

Government and political environment stability is key factor in applying healthy financial and economic policies which directly affects willingness to invest both domestic and international investors. The health of financial intermediaries and markets is crucially dependent on the health of the private and public sectors. Political stability, existence of numerous private companies and individual organizations has been requiring (Jaleta, 2014).

7. Professionals Actors

Stock market is a knowledge intensive sector. It might be tricky to find stock professionals easily (Carmichael and Pomereano, 2002). Brokers and dealers are the key set of actors on an exchange who, as members of the exchange, trade on behalf of an unlimited number of buyer and seller clients (Gebre-Medihin, 2005). Economists, certified accountants, lawyers, and other experienced professionals are required. According to Edosa,(2014),such as a free press, efficient and independent judicial system, corporate lawyers and accountants, professional underwriters and a group of mature institutional investors are require to establish at an early stage of economic development.

8. Accounting and Auditing Standards

To provide necessary and comparable financial information accounting and auditing standard is very important. During the early stages of securities markets development the supply of stocks and bonds is requires experience both human and infrastructural to know the market cycles. First, to ensure that the standards embody the right incentives for all concerned and second, to coordinate adoption of such standards(Chami,.et al, 2009).

9. Technology and Infrastructure

Information technology and infrastructure (electric system) is another determinant factor in the development of stock market to disseminate information. Market is considered to be efficient if information on investment is easily accessible, available and update. The trading system of stock auction and to make online transaction and catch up with other stock exchanges around the globe an automated system is needed. Advances in computer and telecommunications technology contributed to the emergence of global financial markets. Especially Internet-based information technologies, gave investors around the world immediate access to the most recent news and information affecting their investments, sharply reducing information costs (Resnick,2004),Makes it easier to extend trading days and hours due to less cumbersome procedures(Yartey, 2007).

10. Public Awareness and Education and Manpower

Degree of awareness or familiarity about security market is one of determinant factor in stock market. Educate to public, which understands the fundamental rules, the benefits, and the potential pitfalls of participating in the financial system (Chami, et.al. 2009). Educating the public about the role of the stock market can help increase the investor based and improve the liquidity of the stock market (Yartey and Adjasi, 2007) through various mediums like television stations, newspapers, radio stations and public conferences with the general public (Kazarwa, 2015).

II. Macroeconomic Factors

1. Stage of Economic Development and Size of the Economy

An economy must be large enough to support a stock market. It is a necessary prerequisite for the development of a stock market. Without a sufficient supply of shares, trading will be limited and the market may not be economically viable (Reed and Ghossoub, 2013). Economic development is expected to positively affect stock markets. Underdeveloped economies usually have a volatile investment environment, weak institutional and legal frameworks, poor governance, lack of transparency, and above all low levels of per capita income. All these factors impede stock market development and

at times even make the establishment of a stock market superfluous. A small size economy most likely would not have a deep, liquid stock market as such economies are usually characterized by price volatility. Consequently, the amount of capital raised from issuance may be too small to attract potential issuers (El-Walesse, 2013).

2. The Structure of Economy

The structure of the economy the relative proportion of shares representing the primary, industrial and service sectors is an influential determinant of stock market development. In addition, whether the industrial base is dominated by large companies or dominated by small and medium-sized companies has significant implications for the supply of equity. Economies with a large manufacturing base dominated by relatively large companies are more likely to have a sufficient supply of shares (El-Wassal, 2013). Industry sectors are more capital intensive than primary economy as a result the development of financial sector play crucial role to suck up the financial need (Amha, 2017). However, under the primary structure of economy the development of bank can only the supplier of money.

3. Prospects for Economic Growth

Investors only have a small portion of their household income to invest, a fair priced - liquid - market is imperative in order to avoid creating systematic losses for the general public(Rucker,2011)accordingly prospect of economic growth should expected to be positively and favorably developed. Companies usually increase investment and expand productive capacity to meet future expected demand for their products. Sustainable positive rates of economic growth lead to new markets as well as greater opportunities for companies to grow and make profits (El-Wassal, 2013).

4. Private Sector Development

Private sector development is another key factor in the development of stock market. According to Tessema (2003) low level of private sector development and a low level of

market orientation in the economy is problems with the supply and demand for securities, Kanan and Ejigu(2013), letting the private sector develop the capital market would lead to more transparency and more capital allocated to fuel rapid growth. “Access to and ease in movement of financial resources fundamentally influences the prospects for private sector growth in developing countries’ economies. The extent to which existing firms can borrow and grow the ability of emerging firms to act entrepreneurially, their willingness to invest in assets, and the ability to allocate their assets freely are all determining factors to economic growth”(Rucker,2011,p-10).

VI. Stock Market Liquidity

One of the most important aspects of stock market development is liquidity. The primary function of stock markets is to overcome obstacles to liquidity. Modern financial markets are critically dependent on large-scale flows of intraday (within one day) liquidity in payment, clearing, and settlement systems. Under conditions of time-critical liquidity, a settlement payment, delivery of securities, or transfer of collateral must be made at a particular location, in a particular currency, and in a precise time frame measured not in days, but in hours or even minutes (Freire, 2004).

According to Rucker (2011) liquidity is the degree to which an asset or security can be bought or sold in the market without affecting the asset’s market price. Assets that can be easily bought or sold are known as liquid assets. Liquidity is the ability to convert an asset to cash quickly – also known as “marketability”. Liquid markets offer a number of benefits. Among, render financial assets more attractive to investors can transact in them more easily, allow investors to switch out of equity if they want to change the composition of their portfolio; permit financial institutions to accept larger asset-liability mismatches; allow companies to have permanent access to capital through equity issues; allow a central bank to use indirect monetary instruments and generally contribute to a more stable monetary transmission mechanism (El-Wasal, 2013).

VII. listed Companies

The securities of all the companies are not bought and sold on a stock exchange.

Companies have to meet the requirements of the exchange in order to have their stocks and shares listed and traded. The listing requirements may vary from one country to another in terms of the size of company, earning records, number of years in the business, number of shares outstanding. For example to be listed on the New York Stock Exchange, company must have issued at least a million shares of stock worth of \$100 million and must have earned more than \$10 million over the last three years. the main importance of listing is to access to a wider pool of finance, improved marketability of shares, transfer of capital to other uses, enhancement of the company image, and facilitation of growth by acquisition: (Vincent and Musonera,2008). For example a well known non-U.S. companies as Sony, Toyota Motor, Fiat, Telefonos de Mexico, KLM, British Petroleum, Glaxo, and Daimler are directly listed and traded on the New York Stock Exchange. At the same time, U.S. firms such as IBM and GM are listed on the Brussels, Frankfurt, London, and Paris stock exchanges. Such cross border listings of stocks allow investors to buy and sell foreign shares as if they are domestic shares, facilitating international investments Resnick(2004). Companies and firms are source of supply issued shares and must meet the listing requirements. A stock exchange is publicly traded based market regulations (El-Wassal, 2013).

VIII. Level of per capita GDP

“The sound macroeconomic environment and sufficient high income level, GDP- per capital, domestic saving, domestic investment, are important determinants of stock market development in emerging market”(Garcia and Liu,1999) as cited by (Yartey & Adjasi,2007,p-16). Economic growth and per capita GDP are key determinants of stock market development. Higher economic growth rates allow more people to invest in shares. A rise in per capita income increases an individual’s ability to save or invest and risk-sharing behavior (El-Wassel, 2013). In their search for higher returns, individuals may shift from deposits into bank accounts to investment in shares. The higher the per capita GDP and the greater the wealth per capita, the more investment there will be in stock markets, and the more liquid that market will be.

IX. Institutional Investment

Stock market development requires a deep and diverse investor base. The investor base

should be diversified and composed of institutional investors (e.g. mutual funds, pension funds and insurance companies) and other financial institutions dealing in different levels of risk and targeting different economic sectors. These institutional investors can play a crucial role in the accumulation of funds and their channeling into stock markets (El-Wassal, 2013). Establishment of stock markets will create another form of asset holding and incentives to diversify asset portfolio capital flows for individuals and companies (Legesse, 2012). Developing countries should first focus on developing contractual saving institutions before establishing a stock market to provide long-term to provide long-term finance to a stock market (Yartey and Adjasi, 2007). A reasonable and active level of participation by institutional investors is of great importance for a stock market. Unless, it, prone to greater risk from individual speculators (Vincent and Musonera, 2008).

X. Size of Stock Market

GDP growth, domestic investment and financial intermediary sector development are determinative in stock market development. There are two main indicators of stock market size: market capitalization and the number of listed companies: Market Capitalization measure of stock market size, which is positively correlated with the ability to mobilize capital and diversify and, companies' past retained profits and future growth prospects so that a higher ratio to GDP can signify growth prospects as well as stock market development Levine and Zervos, 1998b, Bekaert et al, 2001; Rajan and Zingales, as cited by (El-Wassal, 2013). Whereas; growth of number of companies, capacity of saving due to higher economic growth, and infusing higher capital to various economic sectors should be considering (Ejigu and Kannan, 2013).

III. Monetary and Fiscal Policy Factors

Monetary and Fiscal Policy

Well-organized monetary policies can facilitate stock market development to ensure greater confidence in the stability of the economy as macroeconomic volatility magnifies the asymmetric information problem. Interest rates have a critical effect on the desirability of shares in an individual's portfolio of assets because investors are

concerned with real returns. Consequently, monetary policies should insure an attractive long-term yield for equities compared to other domestic and foreign investment alternatives (Yartey and Adjasi, 2007). Monetary policy can influence stock market returns via five possible channels, the interest rate, the credit, the wealth effect, the exchange rate and the monetary channel (Mishkin & Eakins, 2006) Furthermore, debt markets provide a tool for central banks to manage the money supply and control inflation(Rucker,2011).

Taxation policies have a great influence on investor participation in stock market trade. Investors are concerned with the after-tax real return on investment. Unequal taxation favoring other alternative forms of investment such as bank deposits would shift investor interest from investing in equities. This includes the distribution before dividends including individual level (El-Wassel, 2013).

2.1.2. Challenge of Stock Market

Stock exchange market is risky unless properly manage. It possibly more a gambling casino than a venue in which funds being raised to finance new ventures and expand existing activities. Without liquid markets or other financial arrangements that, less investment may occur in the high-return project and important role in predicting future growth (Levine and Zervos, 1996). According to Tessema(2003), although stock market serves to increase the national savings rate by creating incentives to invest, and earn higher returns than more such as bank savings deposits but risky investment. As a result, economic cycles are more difficult to predict and create income inequity. Automation is expensive and requires huge budget (Yartey and Adjasi, 2007). Prices on the stock market are not simply determined by discounting the expected future cash flows, which should reflect all currently available information about fundamentals. As the term is depicted by Ruckcer(2011) , share buyers might have to close their investment at an entirely unfair price, resulting not only in a personal loss of assets but also in a significant loss of market trust lead deceived investment. In the research work of Legesse(2012)may affect economic activity through their liquidity. Prices on the stock market are not simply determined by discounting the expected future cash flows.

According to Kannaan and Ejigu(2013) one of the main challenge of stock market is speculations. This irrationality is expected to adversely affect the real sector of the economy as it is in danger of becoming the by-product of a casino (Kannaan and Ejigu, 2013). Study made by El-Wassal (2013) shows restrictions on foreign participation in stock markets may contribute to insufficient depth and liquidity in the market. However, the mode and the sequencing of the entry of foreign investors has to be carefully considered, as experience has shown that there is considerable risk associated with participation by nonresidents, who have access to alternative investments and thus may manifest more volatile demand. Institutions factors, such as corporate lawyers and accountants, a free press, an efficient and independent judicial system, professional underwriters and a group of mature institutional investors are difficult to establish at an early stage of stock market development (Edosa, 2014).

Stock liquidity may negatively influence corporate governance by encourage investor myopia. Since investors can easily sell their shares, more liquid stock markets may discourage investors from having long-term investment commitment. Generate perverse incentives, financial engineering rather than creating new wealth through organic growth, particularly in developing country a weaker regulatory institutions and greater macroeconomic (IMF, 2014). A lack of foreign and domestic investors, lack of investment in domestic industries, lack of domestic savings, and low availability of liquid capital, small size of companies, all make it more difficult to establish a successful stock exchange (UNCTAD, 2017).

2.2.Review of Empirical Evidence

I. Stock market in African

In most African countries stock markets are their small size and low levels of liquid by global standard. Africa's smaller markets tend to float between 10 and 20 percent of GDP. The exchanges are small relative to their own economy. Even the older markets in Zimbabwe, Kenya, and Nigeria are typically less than one-third the size of the economy (Musonera and Vincent, 2008). There has been a considerable development in the African capital markets since the early1990s. However, still small with few listed

companies and low market capitalization. Have helped in the financing of the growth of large corporations but there is little evidence of broader economic benefits (Yartey and Adjasi, 2007). According to Tessema review (2003), with the exception of South Africa, African stock markets are extremely small by world standards. Apart from South Africa accounted for only few per cent of world stock market capitalization (Knanann & Ejigu, 2013).

According to Rueceker(2011) there are many countries that have stock markets in Africa. South Africa Stock Market is the oldest stock market in the continent and was launched in 1887 but Nairobi, 1954. According to African capital market watch (2017) However, Johannesburg Stock Exchange (South Africa), Nigeria Stock Exchange; Casablanca Stock Exchange (Morocco) and Egypt Stock Exchange have notable contributions their economy having > \$100bn market cap.

II. Review of Rwanda's Stock Market (RSM)

Rwanda and Ethiopia in particular are characterized by high growth economies post-1990s with significant state involvement and the formal institutions of democracy, but deeply troubling patterns of domestic governance. Rwanda and Ethiopia:

- “Developmental state,” the poster children for developmental states the East Asian countries (Matfess, 2015). Characterized by government interventions into the economy.
- Uneasy marriage of unfastened-market place ideology and full-size government intervention. However, Rwanda implements stock trade marketplace policy considering January, 2011.

1. Political and Economy of Rwanda

Describing political economy is very essential to know the reason of why RSM was established. After the 1994 Genocide, Rwanda has made great strides towards making up for its economic loss, achieving growth of nearly 6% in 2000 and an average growth of nearly 10% since 1995 (Wameyo, 2005) as cited by(Musonera,2014). Rwanda national strategy plan is middle income country and high-income country status by 2035 and

2050, respectively. The Vision will be affected through a series of seven-year National Strategies for Transformation (NST1). A five-year (2013-2018) national strategy is to robust economic and social performances.

Rwanda's capital market was established in 2011 and a secondary market form is an integral market part. Before its establishment, the Rwanda Capital Market Advisory Council was created in 2007. The Council first established to develop the capital market in Rwanda, facilitate the trading of debt and equity securities, enable securities transactions and also to regulate the Rwanda Securities Exchange. The Capital Market Authority (CMA) was established under the Capital Market Act of 2011 to guide the development of capital markets (Cyuzuzo, 2018).

2. Type of Rwanda Stock Market

The RSE is still a young exchange, the youngest in East Africa. Trading began in 2011. Bond listings, exchange currently lists equity shares of seven companies. From listed companies the government owns 20%, while the remaining is owned by brokers and other stakeholders. Out of eight listed companies, four of them are foreign owned. Transactions are carried out manually and cleared electronically through a central securities depository system that is managed by the Central Bank. The government also launched the long-term debt issuance program in 2014. This program consists of issuance of government treasure bonds to the public to increase new products available on the RSE to attract new investors and thus contribute to the development of the stock market (Cyuzuzo, 2018).

Four of listings companies were cross-listed Kenyan firms, whose stock is primarily traded on the Nairobi Securities Exchange (NSE). The latest Kenyan firm to be cross-listed on the RSE is Equity Bank, which began trading in Kigali in February 2015. The three Rwandan firms that have listed shares are the government-majority-owned Bank of Kigali, the beverage company Bralirwa (a subsidiary of Heineken), and most recently, Crystal Telecom, which listed. With the addition of Equity Bank and Crystal Telecom, the market capitalization of the RSE now exceeds 3 trillion RWF (about \$4.2 billion).

3. Basic Concept of Rwanda Stock Market (RSM):

To develop economic growth the Government of Rwanda has taken measures to expand and reinforce the financial sector by established Rwandan capital market as one of the remedies incorporate stock exchange market (Musumera, 2014). The major goals are that the country will achieve middle-income status by 2020. RSE was officially launched on 31 January 2011. Rwanda has one stock exchange that is recognized by the government. This exchange operates through a number of electronically linked counters at different locations thus making it a national trading system. It aims at helping small companies and start-ups to overcome the problems of raising capital through public issues at exorbitant costs. It also helps investors to overcome the problems of ill-liquidity, inaccessibility, delayed settlements and transfers that abound in traditional stock exchanges (Cyuzuzo, 2018). RSE is 60 per cent owned by brokers, 20 per cent by the Government of Rwanda and 20 per cent by other institutional shareholders.

4. Institutional Arrangement of RSM

a. legal framework

CMA has been conducting business under seven laws. Among the investment code, incentives regarding the capital market, governing the holding and circulation of securities, governing the establishment and creation of trusts and trustees, establishing the capital market, regulating collective investment schemes and regulating the capital market business in Rwanda. Further, Government of Rwanda adopted an institutional and regulatory framework to support CMA's development and since 2014 it has launched the government's long-term debt issuance program (Cyuzuzo, 2018).

b. Organization system

The Rwanda Stock Exchange Board is comprised of 7 members distributed as follows:

- Government of Rwanda has one representative
- Members have three representatives
- Institutional investors have one representative
- Members of the public and/or professional bodies have one representative
- Listed companies have one representative

Institutional set-up: Rwanda market advisory council, Rwanda Cooperation Agency, Rwanda Association of Insurers, Rwanda Association of Bankers, and Rwanda Association of Microfinance Institutions are active role players under financial market.

For capital-market integration, the council oversees a number of technical working groups that deliberate how to resolve differences in legal frameworks and market infrastructure among RSM members. Based on this work, the council announced several capital-market directives in 2015(Annual report, 2017).

5. Economic contribution of Stock Market to Rwanda

1.Structure of Rwanda Economy:

For a long time now, a large part of the Rwandan population has been engaged in agriculture which is mostly subsistence and remains the main source of employment in Rwanda. More than 80 percent of economically active workers were employed in agriculture, with only 17 percent of Rwandans living in cities. Rwanda currently has one of the least urbanized populations in Africa. According to Rwanda CSA/(2017) the Rwandan gross domestic product reached Frw 6,618 billion in 2016 up from Frw 5,956 billion in 2015, and like many years since 2011 the services sector had a large share of contribution to the economic growth (47 per cent of total GDP). The agriculture sector contributed 31 per cent of the GDP while the industry sector contributed 17 per cent of the GDP. This is also the reason why though this sector employs a large number of people; it contributes very little to economic growth in the country (Cyuzuzo, 2018). Real GDP growth by sector 2017, Agriculture 6.7%, Industry, 4.4% and Service 8% annual rate (World Bank, 2018).

2.Stages and Development of Ruanda Capital Market and RSM

- Issued IPO which is government bond
- The government decided to sell its 20 per cent stake in Bank of Kigali (BK) to the public and the bank simultaneously raised new capital which was equivalent to 25 per cent of the company's capital.
- In 2013 the government issued sovereign bonds worth US\$ 400 million the country led to a massive over-subscription of the sovereign bonds at 650 per cent. The bonds have a maturity of ten years at a fixed interest rate of 6.875 per cent.

- In the same year CMA assisted in the establishment of the Rwanda National Investment Trust (RNIT). Being a big player in capital market development the government published its bond issuance program in February 2014 to come to the market every quarter.
- In May 2014, the International Finance Corporation (IFC) issued a 5-year bond worth Frw 15 billion. This bond nicknamed ‘Umuganda’ was the first placement by a non-resident issuer in Rwanda’s domestic capital market. It was issued following the IFC program which was established to support capital market development in the region.
- Orders were received from different public and private institutions including pension funds, insurance companies, banks and other financial institutions
- In February 2017, the Government of Rwanda through the Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning sold its 19.81 per cent shares in I&M Bank Rwanda Ltd. to the public through an IPO (Cyuzozu, 2018).
- The government also launched the long-term debt issuance program in 2014. This program consists of issuance of government treasury bonds to the public to increase new products available on the RSE which will attract new investors and thus contribute to the development of the stock market (Musnemera, 2014).

3. Market Capitalization and Investors Participation

By end of 2016, market capitalization stood at US\$ 3.47 billion, up from \$3.3 billion. of December, 2017 there were 17,077 active investors recorded and domestic investors were 81%; other East Africans 16% and 3% were international. This translated into an increase of 7.9% in terms of new investment accounts. Rwanda Government provides fiscal incentives for listing. This includes zero per cent capital gains tax and five per cent dividends tax (down from 15 per cent). Currently 10 brokers are members of the RSE (UNCTAD, 2012).

Figur 2.1 : Market participation by end of 2017

Source: RSE annual report 2017

4. Ruanda Share Development

Figure 2.2 The share of all indexes from January to December, 2017 4.8% to Rwanda Share Index (RSI) went up 12.9 %.

Source RSE 2017 report

E. Opportunities and Challenge of RSE

Opportunities

According to RSM annual report (2018) some other opportunities regarding the establishment of a stock market in Rwanda include: Regional integration, Diaspora resources to be channeled into the stock market, the entrepreneurial spirit of Rwandans and Geographic advantage with Rwanda being the center of East Africa. Untapped market, availability of strong technical assistance, modernized electronic payment system, presence of foreign banking institutions, establishment of business development fund, and East African integration.

Availability of high-tech products such as mobile money transfers, and internet banking included. In addition, strong political will and strategy: financial sector development, national savings mobilization strategy, savings and credit cooperatives strategy, national microfinance implementation strategy, payments systems framework and strategy are mentioned. Increased oversight and supervision of laws and governing of central bank, development of banking industry, payment systems, capital markets, collective investment schemes, mortgages, and launch of mobile money.

Challenges

Challenges which is facing by RSM that need to be addressed such as a to savings rate, a complex tax regime, a small economy and the structure of companies that are family owned and the absence of financial intermediaries, financial advisory services, investment banks and so on (Cyuzuzo, 2018). The following challenges are listed under RSM:

1. Low Domestic Saving and tax regime:

The low domestic savings rate is probably due to low income (real GDP per capita is around US\$ 230) used rather for consumption than for saving, having a complex tax regime from taxes on goods and services, external trade imbalance, income, property, customs taxes to value added taxes are obstacles to attract more investors.

2. Absence of Financial Intermediaries:

Not only lack of financial intermediaries is an obstacle but also lack of merchant banks, financial advisory services and investment banks which are vital to the successful functioning of stock exchange markets.

3. Lack of Adequate Accounting and Auditing Systems:

The existence of a reliable financial accounting system is an important factor in the development of stock exchanges. The authorities are conscientious of the necessity to address deficiencies in accounting and auditing system. At RSM one reason of having

with a small listing company is companies do not meet the minimum requirement especially the financial statement of the consecutive of the three years.

4. Family Owned Companies:

The structure of companies that are family owned is also a hindrance to the creation of a stock market in Rwanda. Large number of businesses that are family owned and which are likely to have enough resources to issue shares. However, whose managers may fear losing control by opening up their businesses to public ownership (lack of corporate governance). Generally, the main factors limiting the supply of equities include the unwillingness of small, family-owned businesses to reduce ownership and the perception by many companies. As a result, these firms cannot be for any use to the stock market.

5. Lack of Information

The lack of public awareness with stock markets is the major barrier to corporate participation in many African stock exchanges. Most of the Rwandan public is not familiar with negotiable instruments. As the project of launching the stock exchange in Rwanda, many people do not know enough about the stock market. Generally, there is lack of information on the roles, functions and operations of the stock exchange. The public should be sensitized about benefits associated with the securities market and encouraged to participate in individual and collective investments.

6. Infrastructure

The market infrastructure is underdeveloped; especially the payment system is traditional, settlement and delivery using a manual system. The manual trading system is slow, costly and limits the range of products that can be provided. It also delays international integration of the market. However, in Rwanda, infrastructure 75 per cent of the population with access to internet and the Government has taken the lead in developing the ICT sector through the installation of advanced applications and their integration into governmental processes.

According to Annual report (2018) the following challenges are stated: relatively small financial market, low investment, low penetration of financial institutions: particularly in rural areas lack of diversified products, limited product innovations, lack of demand-

driven products, lack of skilled and specialized professionals. Most financial institutions are located in urban areas. Further, Lack of education on financial products, limited credit to the private sector, limited products and services comparable are stated and, instability of international market.

7. Professionals

Another important issues regarding RSM only a few skilled and experienced investment and lack of awareness analysts in the region. This results in dependence on short term bank loans. This inaccessibility to long term credit reduces corporate profitability, thus limiting the number of companies that would wish to list stocks in to the stock market. It was further established in this study that lack of awareness is one of the major challenges faced by Rwanda Stock Exchange.

III. Review of Stock Market in Ethiopia

The history of stock market in Ethiopia goes back to the **1960s**, when the government policies were designed to attract investment. During Imperial period government focused the development of private sector and provided incentives. These attracted foreign companies. Regarding the finance sector, state owned and foreigner owned banks, and insurance companies were active. Among, Addis Ababa Bank, Banko di Napoli and Banko diRoma were some of them (Amha, 2017).

During the Imperial period there were signs for the establishment of a stock exchange. State bank of Ethiopia in 1956 facilitated the first public subscription share company called Ethiopian Abattoirs. However, there was no specific law and organized legal entity to deal with stock exchange. National Bank, as the then state Bank of Ethiopia pioneered the establishment of a share exchange department in 1960. A share dealing which was introduced in 1960 had the objectives to mobilize the equity capital from a broad range of sources and spreading ownership over wider variety of individual and institutions (NBE, 1998).

By 1965, because of the growth of the economy and the increment of the number of share companies, security market known as the ‘Share Dealing Group’ established. The group was consisted of six institutions named National Bank, Addis Ababa Bank, Commercial

Bank, Development Bank, Investment Bank of Ethiopia, Sabean Utility Corporation, and a certain individual named Mr. Alfred Abel. However, these ended with the coming of the Derg in the year 1975 (Amha, 2017).

When the Derge regime started in 1975, the government nationalized all private companies. Again the market liberalization process started in 1990s. According to Rucker(2011) When EPRDF took power in May 1991, it started promoting free market economy by swift reform program. Since 1992 the government of Ethiopia made an economic reform such as tariffs eliminated, quota constraints relaxed, licensing procedures simplified, foreign exchange controls eased, compulsory grain delivery and forced membership to cooperatives discontinued, a privatization process begun, private banks authorized, interest rates decontrolled, and an inter-bank money and foreign exchange market introduced. Thus, macroeconomics, structural and institutional strategy and program have had been implementing. Sustainable Development Plan and Poverty Reduction Program (SDPRP) 2002-2005, Plan for Accelerated and Sustainable Development to End Poverty (PASDEP) 2006-2009, Growth and Transformation Plan I and II(2009/2010-2014/15 to 2015/16-2019/20)(Amha,2017).

Commodity exchange is one type of financial market. Ethiopia Commodity Exchange (ECX), was registered as a commercial entity in March 2008. The exchange was established as a demutualized entity/model/. The law is explicit that the exchange's management is independent and autonomous. The corporate governance structure established on a Board of Directors made up nearly equally of private and public actors. Meaning the owners, members, and management were separate by law, and set up as a unique public-private partnership to balance the interests of its promoter, the Government of Ethiopia, and the private traders. ECX does not pay any dividends or receives any earnings. But shares governance and control of management with private stakeholders, bears the risks associated with the entity. Ethiopian coffee farmers receive 70 percent of the final price, rather than the 38 percent in the years before ECX because of better price negotiation (Gebre-Medihin, 2012). However, currently a group of professionals composed of both local and foreign has been undertaking a study in contribution with IMF to prepare a ten year roadmap of the establishment of stock market in Ethiopia.

Summery

Capital markets may be classified as primary markets and secondary markets. In primary markets, new bond or stock issues are sold to investors via the mechanism known as underwriting. In the secondary markets, existing securities are sold and bought among investors or traders, usually on a stock exchange. The history of stock market tracks back to the 17th century has been operating in various forms. History told as Ethiopia had stock market during the Imperial era. Stock market promote private sector development, enhance competition among banks, improves corporate governance, rewards sound economic policies and creates tools to conduct monetary policy. stock market create: Investment horizons: by providing ability to saving mobilizations as means of exiting investment, Transparency: helps to address information symmetry and through the initial listings; Investor protection: by rules of the exchange, combined with relevant securities market regulation, Pooling funds: by bringing together a large and diverse set of investors. For Small and Micro Enterprises by listing, create competition among Banks, increase volume of remittances, improves corporate governance.

However stock exchange market policy is not developed in the vacuum. It is risky and there are many determinant factors which must be meeting before establishing. Out of them institutional such as regulatory policy and legal framework, institutions and organizations framework, require. Beside, macroeconomic factors such as stage of economy, size of economy and issue of per capital income is main one, includes monetary and fiscal policy.

2.3. Conceptual framework

Figure 2.3 A Framework for the Development of Stock Markets

Source: adopted from El-Wassal, 2013

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the research methodology that was adopted throughout the research in order to meet the research objectives. Therefore, research approach, data type and source, the method of data collection, the sampling design, and method of data analysis employed in this study presented in the following section, respectively.

3.2. Research design and method

In order to attain the objective of the study and answer the research questions both qualitative and quantitative research design was employed. Creswell (2014) stated that mixed method research is an approach to inquiry involving collecting both qualitative and quantitative data. Then integrating the two forms of data and using distinct designs that may be involve philosophical assumptions and theoretical combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches frameworks. The core assumption of this form of inquiry is that the mixed approach provides a more complete understanding of the research problem. Qualitative research method was conducted to explore the key informants experience and knowledge in in-depth and details. One of the strengths of using qualitative method is that, the data generated focuses on perceptive responses, contextual meanings and topic important to the participants.

3.3. Data Type and Source

The types of data used in this study include both primary and secondary. Primary data sources were key informant selected from highly relevant institutions such as National Bank of Ethiopia, Policy Research Institute, Accounting and Auditing Board of Ethiopia and Addis Ababa Chamber of Commerce that have major stake in stock exchange market policy. In addition, in-depth review of various documents such as literature, policy proceeding, official statistical reports , books, journals , relevant workshop seminar papers, magazines annual and quarter reports, newspapers, proclamations, published and unpublished resources, MA thesis's and different websites were used as a secondary

resource of data and information used for drafting this study.

3.4. Method of Data Collection

Both qualitative and quantitative data collection methods were employed. Reason behind this is in order to employ the mixed approach which helps to confirm findings from different data sources. The data collection tools designed from this study was key informant interview with unstructured questioner, document analysis and case story.

3.4.1. Key Informant Interview

Primary data were collected by interview with twenty two key informants with a multidimensional detail discussion from National Bank of Ethiopia, Ethiopian Development research/Policy Research Institute/, Addis Ababa Chamber of Commerce, Accounting and Auditing Board of Ethiopia and One from Committee of Economic adviser Prime Ministry office via e-method. The discussion was mainly focused on relevant issues with: role of stock market, challenges to establish stock market in Ethiopia, current level of economic development to implement stock market, prospect to establish the market and the government commitment to establish.

3.4.2. Case Story

Towards achieving the stated objective, the study explored the experience of Rwanda Stock Market. In addition, the experiences of other African countries generally reviewed as empirical evidence on.

3.4.2.1. Rationale for selecting Rwanda

Ethiopia and Rwanda are countries which are labeled under Sub Saharan Region that adopt developmental state model. In countries that adopt such a model, the government intervention is strong in any development process. Beside, According to World Bank: ‘Global Economic prospect’ (2019), Rwanda has maintained a steady 7.33% annual growth rate over the course of 18 years (2000-2018), Ethiopia, as well one of the fastest growing economy in East Africa. While, International Monetary Fund (2019) economic

outlook: the best performing African countries will be: Ethiopia by 8.3% as well as Rwanda 7.8%. By the same token, both countries are particularly impressive increase in GDP between 2005 and 2015, average growth rates at 9.7 and 8%.

3.4.3. Document Analysis

To conduct this research document analysis method also employed for those data which were collected from secondary sources. This helps to examine concept and historical patterns of stock market, key institutional and policy frameworks, macroeconomics factors and challenges regarding stock market. Further, policy and strategy documents, proclamation, annual reports, workshop documents, policy proceeding, newspapers and magazines, public media, parliamentary testimonies, internet were analyzed. Beside, to conduct and compare the documents that contain similar information against the data collected from the aforementioned methods. Accordingly, collected both forms of data at roughly the same time, then, integrates the information in the interpretation of overall results explained and described. Time dimension of this study is cross-sectional research design. The researcher collected all the necessary data that are more relevant for this study at a single time.

3.4.4. Identifying Dynamic Key Actors

3.4.4.1. National Bank of Ethiopia:

NBE is a pioneer and authorized to regulate and supervise the development of finance sector. Beside, responsible in order to review regulatory framework, to conduct assessment and study alternative, legal framework, financial directives, financial infrastructure, to prepare road map, but limited,

3.4.4.2. Ministry of Finance and Economic Cooperative:

Ministry of Finance and Economic Cooperation is a ministry within the cabinet of the Government of Ethiopia. It is responsible for general financial management and financial policy of Ethiopia, in addition to the allocation of economic assistance. The Ministry contributes to the development and public finance efforts of the nation is responsible making changes that can push the public finance and development efforts of the nation

forward.

3.4.4.3. Addis Ababa Chamber of Commerce:

The Addis Ababa Chamber of Commerce & Sectoral Associations (AACCSA) has been established, by the General Notice Number 90/ 1947, in April 1947 as an autonomous, non-governmental, non-political and non-profit organization to act on behalf of its members. The chamber re-establishment with the Proclamation Number 341/2003 further provides the legal framework for the establishment of Chambers of Commerce and Sectoral Associations. AACCSA is a voluntary based member organization with more than 15,000 member business companies. Thus, business companies are the main actor in the development of stock market. The chamber promotes trade and industry, disseminating business information, consulting government and members on economic development and business issues, establishing friendly relationship with similar chambers in other countries, and exchanging information as well as engaging in arbitration in times of disputes among members.

3.4.4.4. Accounting and Auditing Board of Ethiopia:

AABE is a regulatory body established and responsible in order to transparent and understandable financial reporting system applicable to entities in both private and public sectors. In addition, AABE authorized to having a uniform financial reporting law enhances transparency and accountability financial reporting structures of Ethiopia. Responsible to support various building blocks of the economy and to reduce the risk of financial crisis, corporate failure and associated negative economic impacts; it is necessary to ensure that the provision of financial information meets internationally recognized reporting standards but limited.

3.4.4.5. Ethiopian Commodity Exchange (ECX),

A commodity exchange is organized, regulated types of capital market that facilitates the purchase and sale of contracts whose values are tied to the price of commodities. ECX established in 2008, is a new initiative for Ethiopia and the first of its kind in Africa. It is a trading platform where buyers and sellers come together to trade, assure quality

delivery and payment. ECX is a state owned public –private partnership enterprise established as a demutualized corporate entity with clear separation of ownership, membership and management and governed by a Board of Directors.

3.5. Data analysis technique/method

Data analysis techniques focused on results and discussions of research findings based on the data obtained from both primary and secondary source. Data collected through key informant interview, and qualitative quantitative sources including National Bank of Ethiopia, Ministry of Finance and Cooperation, Accounting and Auditing Board of Ethiopia, Addis Ababa Chamber of Commerce ECX and secondary analyzed using simple descriptive and explaining approaches (i.e., side-by-side comparison). “Mixed method writers call this side–by-side approach because the researcher makes the comparison within a discussion” (Creswell, 2014,p-222).This helps to compare and confirm the finding based on qualitative with quantitative.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

4. Introduction

Stock exchange market is a complex trading. The study provides a descriptive analysis about challenge and prospects to establish a well-functioning stock market in Ethiopia. Based on data collection the following sections are presented under the results of the study. Role of stock market, Key determinant factors: institutional factors, macroeconomic factors and policies and prospect of government willingness to establish stock market.

4.1. Role of stock market

According to the key informant interview regarding contribution of stock market with the above aforementioned respective organizations the overall responses is summarized as follows.

“Stock market is an alternative source of capital, encourage domestic saving, long-term economic growth and development, encourage investment, encourage and transparency. Besides, private sector development, privatization public enterprises, Increase ownerships participation and encourage trade and foreign participation (key informant interview, March/2017)”.

One of the interviewees stated that *“stock market expands ownership and develops belongingness as an owner of a company. Beside it develop trade integration”.*

According to IMF (2007) the stock market is expected to accelerate economic growth by providing a boost to domestic savings, increasing the quantity, provide service and the quality of investment. National domestic saving and investment of the country which are critical inputs for sustainable economic growth performed well and help boosting the

economic growth.

This finding confirmed that stock market has a lot of various benefits and contribution in the development process. If a stock market has been properly functioned, it is a hallmark for economic advancement. Now, if the above stated benefit gained from the stock exchange market, why Ethiopia failed to have stock market can be an issue. Besides, what are challenges and determinant factors can be main points.

4.2. Policy and legal framework

There are broad legal policy and regulation framework under US stock market. These regulators regulate financial institutions, markets, and products using licensing, registration, rulemaking, supervisory, enforcement, and resolution powers. Other entities that play a role in financial regulation are interagency bodies, state regulators, and international regulatory body. Main objective is even if diverse goals, even if which vary from regulator to regulator: market efficiency and integrity, consumer and investor protections, capital formation or access to credit, taxpayer protection, illicit activity prevention, and financial stability (Labonte, 2017).

Despite a lot of benefit stock market have, it is a risky investment and having a probability of losing an investment in case the company is in trouble. But there are also mechanisms to prevent stock market from risk. Thus, stock market is strongly regulated investment. Currently there is no policy coverage, legal framework and law regarding stock exchange in Ethiopia. To prevent systematic risk, to ensure market efficiency and transparency, to protect investor's confidence legal framework is precondition.

International Finance Corporation (IFC) has introduced seven regulatory indicators to assess stock markets: Whether companies listed in a stock market, price-earnings information, accounting standards, the quality of investor protection, Securities and Exchange Commission, restrictions on capital repatriation and domestic investment by foreigners.

Ethiopian commercial law which was enacted in 1960 remained has been dormant yet

and having with many gaps to implement stock market in Ethiopia. Accordingly, this law requires amendments to function a well-established stock trade. Overall, important to be considered a number of regulatory issues before formulating policy and legal issues of stock market. The respondents from the above aforementioned sectors revealed that missing to having strong legal framework the consequence could be very destructive.

As pointed out by key informant interviewee from National Bank of Ethiopia, Policy Research Institute, Accounting and Auditing Board of Ethiopia (AABE) and Addis Ababa Chamber of Commerce, the overall response was no difference regarding the existence of legal policy and framework. In spite of the fact that, the most primary requirements to establish well-functioning stock market is the existence of policy and legal framework. Regarding the legal framework, key informants from National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) and Policy Research Institute has been emphasized that enacting appropriate laws and establishes regulatory institutions of the securities market should get the appropriate attention by the government before establishment. Legal infrastructure and governance system development with the objective of protecting right of investors, creditors and ensuring transparency in the management of listed companies and all transactions are required.

Secondary data which was collected from National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) shows that the Bank had study on “Feasibility of Establishing of Securities Exchange Market in Ethiopia” by 1995. Beside, a draft with securities and exchange proclamation also prepared. However, it was not endorsed by the Government. Rational at the back of the confined enforcement become, by the time the economy and financial system were not advanced to set up stock market.

In addition, the qualitative data which gained through key informant interview with one of the above stated respective government institution is emphasized:

“The demand for stock markets was not that strong previously and, as a result, little progress was made on building the necessary institutions for stock market development. Currently, the most important challenge is inability to have a strong regulatory environment”(key informant

interview, April/2017).

The following key legal regulatory documents declared in Rwanda Stock Market (RSE.), legal rules, fee structure, Rwanda stock exchange small & medium enterprise market segment rules, administrative and pecuniary sanctions applicable to participants' rules and so on stated as pre- requirements to participate in RSE (www.rse.rw).

To sum up, stock is a risky investment which needs strong policy and legal frameworks. It is mandatory endorsing policy, rules and regulations the establishment of stock market regards to protect stock actors (both buyers and sellers) under stock exchange trade. Therefore, based on the KII respondent, document and literature review made in chapter two of this study confirmed that favorable policy and legal framework needed. So, the government should critically examine to having strong legal policy and frameworks.

4.3. Regulatory Public Institution

In theory financial system is multifarious. Different types of financial institutes including private sectors such as banks, insurances, and pension funds strongly regulated by the government. The most important financial institution in the financial system is the central bank. Stock market requires public regulatory institution. This regulatory public institution (authority/commission) is responsible to control not only every activity but also responsible providing license to those stock market participants.

According to Labonte (2017) studied U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) is independent public agency responsible to protect and maintain the integrity of security markets. Main function is assuring a constant, timely, and accurate flow of information to investors, prompting discourses of information and reducing asymmetric information rather than determining the strength or well-being of any particular firms. The commission is the promotion of transparency in securities markets and thus the protection of investors from fraud or corporate malfeasance. The SEC is tasked with providing guidance to corporations regarding U.S. accounting rules. Congress authorizes the commission to bring civil charges against

firms thought to have committed fraud or other accounting wrongdoings. Among other oversight roles, the Commission regulates the derivatives clearing houses that bring together buyers and sellers of futures contracts. Approves and regulates the organizations responsible for actually executing futures trades; and monitors buyers and sellers in an attempt to ensure against fraud and other violations.

According to one of the interviewees from NBE,

“The main objective of regulatory institutes are to take responsibility for protecting investors and the same time individuals against fraud and deceptive, facilitating efficiency, formation, promotes full public disclosure, controlling practices in the market, sharing of market-related information, and monitors corporate action through established securities rules and regulation. NBE can be a good example regarding the efficiently controlling approach to financial sectors such that is commercial banks and insurances besides, to provide registration statement, periodic financial report and relevant service and activity expected. Regulatory bodies should be responsible to supervise stock actors in the securities markets (just like NBE has been doing)(key informant interviewee, April/2017)”.

Lesson from Rwanda indicates that, Rwanda Capital market Advisory Council created in 2007. The Council first establish to expand the capital marketplace in Rwanda, facilitate the trading of debt and fairness securities, allow securities transactions and additionally to adjust the Rwanda Securities change. Finally Rwanda capital market was established in 2011 with appropriate rules, regulation and responsibility.

The proclamation that established the ECX (No. 550 / 2007) mandates the ECX to set out its own rules of governance for various operations. At the same time, proclamation No. 551 / 2007 Ethiopia Commodity Exchange Authority (ECEA) developed the list of regulations, governing membership, management, trading, warehousing, clearing and settlement, and other operations of ECX by consistent with global best practices. Experts regularly conduct trends on market surveillance and audits and investigations on market operations. These practices are designed to protect the market from manipulation,

excessive speculation, fraud or other malpractice. The ECX has the authority to oversee the following: Rules of the exchange and regulation of exchange-traded contracts, conduct investment advisors, consulting companies, law practices, accounting and audit professionals and so on which is relevant to commodity exchange market.

Main duties and responsibility of SEC in USA: division of Corporate Finance: is responsible from collecting the many documents that public companies are required to file, division market regulation: establishes and maintains standards for an orderly and efficient market by regulating the major securities market participants, division of investment management: oversees and regulates the investment management industry and division of enforcement investigates violation of any of the rules and regulations established by the other divisions. Besides, require insider file reports whenever shares are brought or sold and to prohibit any form of market manipulation.

This finding implies that to establish well-functioning stock market, mandatory to set up an organization or public regulatory body who is responsible to regulate the market within all stock stakeholders and actors. Therefore, based on the literature review made in chapter two of this study and data collected from respondents confirmed stock market requires a regulatory body. So, the government should critically examine to having strong regulatory body with the idea of establishing stock market who certified stock actors and every activity against entity. Public body flourishes solid legal and institutional frameworks. Authorized to register, to review, to suspend or terminate stock participants as ECX has been doing.

4.4. Professional Actors

Stock market is a knowledge intensive business. In respect to professional actors each and every transaction is happening with the help of professionals. Professional actors like stock brokers and dealers, economists, certified accountants and auditors, lawyers, and other experienced professionals are required as the key set of actors. In a well-established stock market individuals are restricted to sale and buy stock directly. Financial intermediaries play critical role regarding the trade. According to Carmichael and

Pomerleano(2002) studies buying and selling stock requires license and financial intermediaries. For example, the broker must have best stock market knowledge, skill, professional ethics and belief. Dealer under the transaction of stock business build an inventory those purchase shares from individuals when they wish to sell. Both dealers and brokers may act purely as agents of their clients or trade as owners of inventory of financial assets. In any stock market Key players such as security dealers and brokers conducted trading in secondary markets.

Brokers are pure middlemen who act as agents for investors in the purchase or sale of securities. Their function is matches buyers with sellers, a function for which they are paid brokerage commissions.

Dealers: in contrast brokers, dealers link buyers and sellers by standing ready to buy and sell securities at a given prices. Therefore, dealers hold inventories of securities and make their living by selling these securities for a slightly higher price than they paid for them. But there is a probability the price can rise or fall based on bid.

Investors: also called market orders, to buy a security at a current market price. They may also set limits to the lower price at which they will sell their security or the highest price they will pay for a security, also called limited order.

One of key informant interviewees from NBE, were pointed out that *“during the first implementation phase may be difficult to get those actors easily”*. However, the suggestion stated by another a key informant interviewee from Policy Research Institute shows that,

“About capacity of experts and companies, it generally should not be issues if other things are in place because they don’t even need be Ethiopians” (Key informant interview, April/2019).

The experience of Rwanda stock market has been shows, as one of the main challenges absence of financial intermediaries. RSM have only a few skilled and experienced investment and lack of awareness and skilled professionals in the stock business. Accordingly, they dependence on short term bank loans and has been limiting the number

of companies that would wish to list stocks market.

The key finding from KII, document and Literature review is that the existence of financial intermediaries in stock trade indicates depository and investment bank which they should plays a great role in stock trading.

4.5. Education and Awareness

As affirmation stock is a not a risk free business and has an effect on the individual wealth and companies' financial assets. Education and awareness has significant impact in stock trade to develop investors' confidence in the sake of their financial decisions. Also helps to develop risk-taking behavior. One main function of stock exchange is bringing together buyers and sellers. Education and awareness plays critical role to minimize potential troubles and risks. There should be relatively fair knowledge between the actors. Education and knowledge centers, research institutes, investment advisers (like investment bank), and security analysts, well-educated financial journalists, brokers and dealers, financial analyst and so on can serve to educate and aware concerning stock business.

One of the respondents revealed that,

“There are no coordinated efforts or centers at the national level to that create knowledge and awareness about stock exchange market. The absence of a national stock market education and awareness strategy can matter the consequence to fragmented and poor function which do not enough to appropriate well-functioning stock market” (KII, April/2019).

Lesson from Rwanda shows that stock exchange conducted by public education sessions in different public and private organizations through seminars, meetings presentations (both domestic and international), radios and TV talks. Training on higher learning Institutions and Universities in Rwanda and abroad are main centers of education and awareness to the majority. Further, learn from the existing international practices.

Regarding education and awareness also one of a key informant interviewee argued,

‘There is so much information asymmetry in the economy and limited society level knowledge and awareness in general. In addition, the regulatory and institutional environment for the proper functioning of stock markets is still weak or non-existent. In such cases, few informed participants in the stock market can potentially abuse the society at large (key informant interview April / 2019’.

To sum up stock market has a major effect on people’s wealth and on companies’ investment decision. It is deserve to provide particular attention to create knowledge and awareness. Understanding how stock market managed is important at any level because there will be many times in our life, as an individual, as an employed or as an owner of the business, a probability to become stock market participant.

4.6. Technology and Infrastructure

Stock trade heavily attached with the development of technology and infrastructure. Accordingly, it is one of the key components in the process of stock market establishment. Many types of infrastructure need to build before establishment. Fast, consistent, sufficient and regular supply of infrastructure is a precondition for its existence. The a modern payment system for clearing and settling securities transactions, automation with advances computer, telecommunications technology, internet-based information provides immediate access to the most recent news and information to investors and Actors. To provide Information symmetrically, to show decision of investor’s value to the prospects of the business, information technology infrastructure is mandatory while the construction requires enormous investment.

Regarding technology and information almost all the respondent in aggregated concluded that the current technology infrastructure and level of improvement may limit the requirement of the stock market. However, they highlighted, it is sufficient to establish a functioning stock market at some level. One of the respondent argued commercial banks and ECX can be example. They can manage their task even the development of

infrastructure has been hindering their transaction.

Development of information and Technology ensure transparency and make all the necessary stock market information available at anytime and anywhere. Underdeveloped infrastructure such as telecommunication technology and electricity creates frequent power outages and interrupting hinders the use of electronic channels and financial transactions. Thus, adversely affects efficiency and slows down stock market development. To know about immediate stock news, listed companies, financial gain and lose, trading volumes and prices, complete registration documentation and fulfill other disclosure requirements.

One of the respondent KII informants revalued that

“Undeveloped stock market is characterized by high information asymmetry and low level of liquidity as a result of poor infrastructure development. A market is considered to be efficient if information on investment is easily accessible”.

Many investors look at the economic growth rates, stock market performance, listed company performance, government policies, and so on, in order to make informed decision on investing in companies' shares. Including, publications, brokers, research report and so on. These trends are also widely circulated by newspapers, TV, internet, and other related popular media. Furthermore, publicly listed companies are obliged to immediately publish any relevant facts or information that might influence the price of their shares such as profit and sales warnings, changes in management or to the board of directors, acquisitions of other companies and the sale of business units.

4.7. Accounting and Auditing Standards

The overall purpose of accounting and auditing standards is to identify proper accounting practice for the preparation of financial statements. Accounting standards specify when and how economic events are to be recognized, measured and displayed. Banks, investors and regulatory agencies, rely on accounting standards to ensure relevant and accurate

information is provided about the entity. Stock market exchange heavily relies on accounting and auditing report. The key informant interviewees argue that the basic problem in relation to establishment of stock market has been financial reporting system. According to one of the interviewees from NBE replied:

“The current financial reporting situation, let alone to establish stock market, (accounting and auditing system) has been basic problem for Inland Revenue Authorities to handle and collect tax properly. Of course by recognizing this, the Ethiopian government established Accounting and Auditing Board of Ethiopia. Thus, it is a good start and truck and can be an outlook to set up reliable stock market information to the near future” (KII April/2019).

Accounting and Auditing Board of Ethiopia (AABE) established under proclamation No. 847/2014. The mission is to support investment and protect the public interest by promoting high quality financial reporting in Ethiopia through appropriate oversight of the accountancy profession, in accordance with local laws and international standards. Under AABE regulation section 5 stated: Promote high quality reporting of financial and related information by reporting entities; Promote the highest professional standards among auditors and accountants; Promote the quality of accounting and auditing services; Ensure the accountancy profession is used in the public interest; and protect the professional independence of accountants and auditors. Countries with strong accounting and auditing standard have opportunity to more a well-functioning financial system.

Following establishment the board facilitated International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) to have been adopted by some selected organizations based on the thresholds in terms their capital. The implementation relies on segregating of different phases of each five year. According to the data which is collected from AABE by the first phase all private banks and insurance, mega public enterprises that have capital more than fifty millions applied IFRS. Accordingly, the first five year report is submitted by those companies to review by AABE.

Findings of the interviews administered to key informants from AABE confirmed that

ABBE is recently established organization. There is inadequacy of professional expertise and skills gap to analyze reports among the IFRS, which is submitted by these companies, reviewing reports not yet started. However, one of the respondents who are working AABE replied they are intended to hire the international consultant who analyses the submitted reports. The respondent from NBE, AACC and AABE emphasized that there is no question about the certification of financial report, and having accounting and auditing standards due to stock market business.

4.8. Financial Intermediaries

4.8.1.1. Central Depository/Depository Institutions/ and Investment banks

In a well-functioning stock market depository institutions are financial intermediaries that accept deposits from individuals and make loans. These institutions include commercial banks: saving and loan associations, mutual saving and loan associations, mutual saving banks and credit unions. Stock market demands a modern trading platform, central security depository, market information dissemination mechanisms and clearing facilities. For example in US stock market only 72 hours has been employed to facilitate stock transaction from buyer to seller and vic'e- verse.

According to Mishkin and Eakins (2006) Investment Banks are firms has assist in the initial sale of securities in primary markets and, as security brokers and dealers , assist in the trading of securities in the secondary markets, some of which are organized into exchanges. Theoretically Investment bank is under the regulation of public regulatory body. One of the main tasks is to ensure that adequate information reaches to prospective investors. Under the investment banking firm's taking ownership of the stock issues by purchasing all of them shares from the issuer to then reselling them in the market. Beside, assist in issuing firms by providing advice, filling documents, and making issues. The Bank plays a critical role in the process of raising funds in primary and secondary markets. Unlike commercial banks, investment banks do not make money through interest of savings and lending. Investment banks assist the issuing companies in preparation of the various documents required to be filed at the regulatory bodies and serve as consultants in the valuation of the companies' shares and in contacting potential

institutional investors to buy the shares.

Experience of ECX shows that, Exchange Central depository of ECX maintains as Exchange Central Depository or Registry of warehouse receipts. one of the main task is issues warehouse receipts, prints copies of receipts, transfers legal titles (transferring Electronic Warehouse Receipts between holders), and cancels receipts. It also maintains separate accounts for every depositor. the secondary data which is collected from ECX shows, currently they are working towards introducing the use of Electronic Warehouse Receipts for the purposes of securing collateral finance or also known as inventory financing in the near future as a central depository system.

Rwanda experience shows that Central Stock Depository service provides by Central Depository Agents (CDAs) and their Settlement Banks. Holding and transfer services were outsourced to the Central Depository and Settlement Corporation (CDSC), which was established in 2011. However, one of the main challenges under RSE is the absence investment banks. Accordingly, normal merchant banking services such as underwriting of equities and bonds, asset management and corporate advisory services do not yet exist.

According to the key informant interviewees from NBE and Addis Ababa Chamber of Commerce revealed that investment bank and depository institutions are necessary organization which is authorized to facilitate investment in stock markets related issues. Thus, they argued, to go in line with this, the government has to consider institutional and set up issues of those organizations.

Table 4.1 Bank Supervision Directorate, NBE, 2018-19, first quarter report

Banks	Branch Network												Capital			
	2017/18								2018/19				2017/18	2018/19		
	Quarter I				Quarter IV				Quarter I				Quarter I	Quarter IV	Quarter I	
	Reg	A.A	Total	%	Reg	A.A	Total	%	Reg	A.A	Total	%	Quarter I	Quarter IV	Quarter I	
1. Public Banks																
Commercial Bank of Ethiopia	1,032	310	1342	30.1	1,051	324	1,375	28.9	1,093	327	1,420	28.5	43,822.4	43,851.8	45,801.6	
Development Bank of Ethiopia	106	4	110	2.5	103	4	107	2.2	103	4	107	2.1	7,692.6	7,676.5	7,778.3	
Total Public Banks	1,098	272	1,452	32.5	1,154	328	1,482	31.2	1,196	331	1,527	30.6	51,515.0	51,528.3	53,580.0	
2. Private Banks																
Awash International Bank	186	161	347	7.8	213	169	382	8.0	224	172	396	7.9	3,811.0	4,210.0	4,594.0	
Dashen Bank	208	134	342	7.7	238	143	381	8.0	245	144	389	7.8	3,426.0	3,725.6	3,898.5	
Abyssinia Bank	139	128	267	6.0	144	140	284	6.0	159	144	303	6.1	2,620.9	3,265.8	3,270.2	
Wegagen Bank	154	98	252	5.6	174	118	292	6.1	197	128	325	6.5	2,824.9	3,195.7	3,196.9	
United Bank	114	109	223	5.0	116	117	233	4.9	126	118	244	4.9	2,234.4	2,579.9	2,586.8	
Nib International Bank	94	113	207	4.6	101	127	228	4.8	113	133	246	4.9	2,630.2	2,991.4	3,114.6	
Cooperative Bank of Oromiya	241	59	300	6.7	270	62	332	7.0	281	65	346	6.9	1,291.0	1,924.6	1,980.3	
Lion International Bank	125	54	179	4.0	145	65	210	4.4	152	68	220	4.4	1,233.3	1,479.7	1,614.2	
Oromia International Bank	165	74	239	5.4	171	89	260	5.5	171	90	261	5.2	1,492.2	1,890.0	1,952.4	
Zemen Bank	12	11	23	0.5	12	13	25	0.5	15	15	30	0.6	1,050.7	1,391.8	1,391.8	
Buna International Bank	88	72	160	3.6	96	80	176	3.7	97	81	178	3.6	1,203.3	1,667.7	1,770.7	
Berhan International Bank	97	87	184	4.1	76	92	168	3.5	101	94	195	3.9	1,624.2	1,936.5	2,022.4	
Abay Bank	112	45	157	3.5	109	53	162	3.4	119	60	179	3.6	1,186.6	1,514.7	1,517.5	
Addis Interational Bank	23	33	56	1.3	24	35	59	1.2	25	37	62	1.2	704.3	789.6	812.0	
Debub Global Bank	19	19	38	0.9	22	21	43	0.9	23	22	45	0.9	490.7	614.3	640.3	
Enat Bank S.C	12	23	35	0.8	15	25	40	0.8	15	25	40	0.8	842.8	1,045.4	1,072.3	
Total Private Banks	1,789	1,220	3,009	67.5	1,926	1,349	3,275	68.8	2,063	1,396	3,459	69.4	28,666.6	34,222.8	35,434.9	
3. Grand Total Banks	2,887	1,492	4,461	100	3,080	1,677	4,757	100.0	3,259	1,727	4,986	100.0	80,181.7	85,751.2	89,014.9	

Source NBE: Bank Supervision Directorate, NBE, 2018-19, first quarter report

The above data shows that the number of banks currently available in Ethiopia. But the data do not show the existence of investment bank which is organized to serve as stock market intermediary.

4.9. Corporate governance

Corporate governance incorporates investor protection; boost investor confidence, transparency and information dissemination. For example NBE has a strong corporate government directive under banking business proclamation No. 592/2008 and amendment directive no.SSB/68/2018. It is document written to mitigate systematic abuse of power by influential persons in the bank and insurance sector that includes the

board of directors, the various board sub-committees, chief executive officers, senior management of companies and influential shareholders, who owns more than two percent of total subscribed capital of the insurer.

Key informant NBE revealed that:

“The interviewee emphasized framework of corporate governance is critical as one of the main concern for stock market. Before establishing stock market the government should come up with vital code of corporate governance. Despite the fact there has been NBE a strong corporate governance law and directive; as well companies must have a clear corporate governance structure and codes before they registered” (KII, April/2019).

Corporate governance also plays critical role to register in companies listing, and increase companies’ value, and transparency in the area of aspects. Better oversight regarding transparency and to increase coordination. Beside, transactions, major shareholders and related parties disclosed under well-functioning stock market.

Regarding corporate governance listed companies have clearly shows the segregation of responsibility between Chairman and Chief Executive Officer. Companies corporate governance should clearly shows shareholders right, general meeting procedures, about the board, audit committee and top management , company by law ,code of conducts and so on.

4.10. Macroeconomic factor

4.10.1. Economic structure

According to National Bank of Ethiopia Annual report (2017/18), agricultural 3.5 percent, Industrial sector showed 12.2 percent output growth and registered 27percent share in GDP. Manufacturing sector increased by 5.5 percent and constituted about 25.3 percent of the industrial output. Construction industry, on the other hand, accounted for 71.4 percent of the industrial output and expanded by 15.7 percent signifying the leading

role of the construction sector in terms of roads, railways, dams and residential houses expansion. Electricity, water and mining & quarrying had 2.6 and 0.7 percent contribution to industrial production, respectively during 2017/18. Service sector continued to dominate the economy as its share in GDP rose to 39.2 percent while its contribution to the GDP growth increased to 43.9 percent. It showed 8.8 percent growth largely owing to the expansion of wholesale & retail trade, Public administration & defense, hotels & restaurants, transport & communication, real estate, renting & business activities.

Figure 4.1 Real GDP Growth by Major Sectors

Source: Plan and Development Commission, 2018

The structure of the economy is the main determinate factor in stock market trade. According to some of interviewees who are aforementioned from the respective organization, regarding economic structure revealed that secondary sector economy is more of capital intensive and required to have a huge amount of capital. While relatively the primary sector the development of banking sector can be the supplier of the required capital. However, industry and service sector economic structure especially manufacturing has been intensively absorbed huge amount of capital. One of the solid reasons having stock market is the development of different economic sector and to mobilize financial need successfully.

The above data confirm how industry and service sector positively has been growing in Ethiopia. The existence of stock market provides access to and easy movement of financial resources for manufacturing and service companies. Well-functioning stock markets are key factors in the producing high economic growth. Activities in stock market also have direct effects on personal wealth and business thus the cyclical performance of the economy. Consequently, the private sector will be developed. Hence, unemployment decreases as a result of private sector development.

4.10.2 Stage of economic development and size of economy

Stock market development is to a large extent dependent on the level of structural and economic development of a country heavily dictates the guidelines for timing, sequencing, and even the feasibility of what can be done in terms of developing local capital markets.

The stage of economic development is one theme on the establishment of stock market. At the early stages of economic development no need establish stock market. Thus, banks and micro financial institutes are enough to cover the financial need. At this point institutions are deprived to implement stock market. During the secondary stage of economic development, the number of companies has grown up. At the same the share of companies increased and financial requirement also increased. Accordingly, companies' specification huge amount of money and difficulty to cover all the financial demand require mobilizing other financial resource. Thirdly, if the economic growth and development reach efficient and full-fledge level, the arrangement of financial sector develop and the financial sector can be matured to establish well functioning stock market to get investment fund. Thus, the levels of economic stage contribute to the establishment of stock market. Size of economy is a positive significance with companies' development.

All key informant interviewee commonly confirmed that, Companies usually increase their investment and expand their productive capacity to meet future expected profit from their products. Accordingly, prospect of economic growth serves as an inducement for companies to obtain financing by issuing IPO and stock to expand business. Thus, the

number of listed companies induces and the number of shares is more available for trading.

According to National Planning Commission (2018) report Ethiopia’s GDP increased from USD 8.2 billion to 2000/2001 to USD 80.60 Billion 2016/17 at current market prices. The high and fast economic growth then able the country achieves a remarkable performance, reaching double that of the Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) countries average real GDP growth.

Figure 4.2. IMF: Regional Economic Outlook

Source: IMF: Regional Economic Outlook

4.10.3 prospect of economic growth and per capital income

One of the determinant factors regarding the establishment of stock market is prospect of economic growth. The Ethiopian economic prospects for FY2018 and the medium term should remain stable, although less spectacular than during 2005/06–2015/16. Annual real GDP growth is projected to hover around 8 percent in FY2018 and the medium term (World Bank, 2018). The government’s macroeconomic policies are expected to remain sound, with moderate fiscal deficits and prudent monetary policy. Although the rate of inflation should remain in the single digits, the inflation differential with competitors may widen and need to be corrected appropriately to preserve Ethiopia’s external competitiveness.

Figure 4.3. IMF: Regional Economic Outlook

Source: IMF: Regional Economic Outlook

According to one of the interviewee, Ethiopian Development Research Institute/Policy Research Institute/pointed out that:

“The current economic structure and level of development may limit the specification and liquidity of the stock market. But, they are sufficient to establish a functioning stock market”(Key informant interview, April/2019).

There are other African countries having stock market but less level of economic development in terms of GDP. Kenya and Uganda are best example. According to African Development Bank economic outlook (2018), Uganda and Kenya GDP growth rate 5.1% were as Ethiopia 8.1% respectively. One of another interviewees support this point by stating that:

“Current economic structure and level of development is sufficient to enable a functioning a stock market. There are risks but managing a stock market is not more difficult than managing a huge country like Ethiopia; and there are countries at a similar stage of development with stock exchange markets. Besides, shares are already in the market which implies the underlying demand is already there”(Key informant interview, March/2017).

4.10.4 Institutional Investors

East African institutional investors are already active participants in the region's capital markets. The chart compares the asset allocation of the Rwandan and Kenyan pension industries as of December 2014. Pension funds and insurance companies are vital for developing and sustaining stock market. For example 84% of the shares of London Stock Exchange Market are held by these institutions. Consequently, they tend to have strong demand for share and long-term bonds (Sptatt, 2009). Thus, suppose leading to a main source of long-term investment funds and to get positive economic growth. According to Ethiopian social security annual report 2018, they collect about 28.45 billion birr from pension fund. However, it is not properly mobilized. Other countries experience shows that pension sectors invest largely in government bonds, real estate, and public equities.

Interestingly, the Rwandan pension sector, which in this chart refers solely to the Rwandan Social Security Board, also invests 16 percent of its assets in unquoted equity securities. On the other hand, nearly a quarter of Rwandan pension assets are allocated to fixed and term deposits at banks. Neither country's pension sector allocates more than 5 percent of assets to corporate bonds.

According to one of the respondent from KII of NBE revealed that

“Government Bonds represent instruments which have long term maturity a ten year and more which usually issued for special purposes. The holders of long term bonds among others include the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE), the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia, the Development Bank of Ethiopia (DBE), Public Servants Social Security Agency and Private Organization Social Security Agency” (KII, April/2019).

In Ethiopia many adults save old age pension but not even to cover medical expenses. Ethiopian social protection schemes are not developed yet. Pension fund can be traded to stock market and can be long-term source of resource as shown the experience of other country having a well-functioning stock market. However reliable and appropriate policy and legal framework is needed to deploy this resource as a source of stock market.

4.10.5 Private Sector Development

The private sector participation in the country's economic development through mobilizing capital, providing employment opportunities, promoting efficient resource management and enhancing productivity has been irreplaceable role. Beside, currently approved Public Private Partnership (PPP) proclamation 1076/2018 which is designed to create a favorable framework to and facilitating the implementation of privately financed projects to support Ethiopian economic growth can have a potential to develop listing companies.

View of this, the Government in its current Growth and Transformation Plan has accorded significant emphasis for the flourishing of private investment both from domestic and external sources through designing appropriate policies and strategies, and creating supporting institutions. In Ethiopia tend to have a limited number large company, few medium sized companies and many small. One of the limitations in the development of private sector is access to finance. World Bank (2016) report shows in average only 40% to all small, medium and large centerpieces has been covered their financial need which was inadequate.

Stock Market is another form of portfolio investment particularly if the private sector is well developed. Small and Medium Enterprises are one of the government strategies to boost economic development and to develop labor intensive sector. However they are not developed as they are expected. They impede and have been failed to having enough resource.

Rwanda experience shows that the structure of companies that are family owned is also a hindrance to the development of a stock market in Rwanda. Large number of businesses that are family owned. One factor limiting the supply of equities includes the unwillingness of small, family-owned businesses to reduce ownership and the perception by many companies.

According to the one respondent of KII of NBE our banks have limited resource. *'It is difficult to cover all financial resource which should be acquired by private sector*

including foreign currency our banks have limited resource'. Stock market promotes private sector development not only by financial resource but also appropriate competition, entrepreneurship. To sum up, that private sector is the main foundation of growth and development. Government provides different incentives, strategies and policies such as Small and Medium Enterprises policy, development of industrial parks and PPP -policy to develop private sector. Thus, stock market can be source of capital if properly managed.

4.10.6 Stock liquidity

Stock is liquid if the market in which it is traded has depth and breadth, and if there are many buyers and sellers. One of the most important aspects of stock market development is liquidity. Stock markets allow companies to have permanent access to capital through equity issues; ability to easily buy and sell securities with low cost. A well- functioning stock markets attract large numbers of buyers and sellers. Some key informant from Policy Research Institute, National Bank of Ethiopia and Addis Ababa Chamber of Commerce revealed that *'liquidity may not occur especially at early stage of establishment. It may arise, it may not be issued and not many transactions will be undertaken. As a result it will limit the volume of active trading may be healed'*.

Liquidity that stock market introduced in to financial system may also have the effect of reducing incentive and return which is expected from the market. Accordingly, they may probity of investors withdraw with their fund at any point. However one of the respondents argued that there is a mechanism to prevent liquidity through professionals such as stock advisers, brokers and dealers who are licensed the market with ethics, appropriate knowledge and skill. In many stoke markets individuals are not allowed to participate in stock business directly but limited to involve with in appropriate financial intermediaries.

For example, Rwanda Stock Exchange was officially launched on 31 January 2011. It was aims at helping small companies and start-ups to overcome the problems of raising capital through public issues at exorbitant costs. Further, to help investors to overcome the problems of ill-liquidity, inaccessibility, delayed settlements and transfers that abound

in traditional stock exchanges. Since then trading operations was taken up by demutualized and had started as registered as a limited company. all through, 60 per cent owned by brokers, 20 per cent by the Government of Rwanda and 20 per cent by other institutional shareholders. From July 2012 to June 2013, 124.2 million shares traded, represent an increase of 94 per cent in money terms and an increase of about 2 per cent in the number of shares traded. The market was driven by the activities on the counters of domestic companies which amounted to 99.9 per cent in the total turnover.

4.10.7 listing company

Stock is strongly controlled business. Companies cannot easily list under stock exchange. To register capital in stock markets, companies must meet the listing requirements. The potential listed companies' required complementary measure to participate on stock trading. According to one of the key informant interviewee who addressed the experience of USA articulated, to participate in American stock exchange the following minimum requirements are requested by Security and Exchange Commission. Among them, certificate from Accounting Oversight Board, Stock exchange board, stock investment insurer and lender Banks, certified financial statement and professional qualifications certificates and ethics.

The listing requirements reflect policy, rules, obligations and procedures governing new applications, proposed marketing of securities and the continuing obligations of issuers.

Participant who engaged in stock trade should be aware that the idea precisely.

By the same token the other key informants pointed out, NBE, present to its draft policy regarding the participation of Ethiopian Diaspora to take part in Ethiopia's to modernize the financial sector and improve the efficiency of remittance flows. Further, current high enthusiasm among foreign investors and program of privatization mega public enterprises is a great opportunity to establish the security markets. Thus, with the opening of such markets the number of companies will issuing shares and get listed in stock exchange then active and liquid market can created. Beside, financial transparency plays a critical role participates stock market to prevent liquidity.

Further, management boarded evaluation and financial query, at least a three year company life or profile, certified audit statement and report, organized companies financial report, certified corporate governance policy, certified lawyers and insurance documents. It illustrates stock market is complex, strong regulation intensive and very difficult task.

According to the interviewee from AACC, well-functioning stock market develop private sector. Consequently, increase the number of companies which will be listed. Under the poor functioning stock market consequently make a poor poorer and rich richer accordingly it creates inequality. Thus, affect those who have low- and fixed-income groups including public servants. Weak and illegal financial system leads to result lower growth rate of stock market.

According to the interviewee from NBE: *“A well-functioning stock market develop private sector. Consequently, increase the numbers of companies which will be listed”*. Under the poor functioning stock market consequently make a poor poorer and rich richer thus it creates inequality. Beside, affect those who have low- and fixed-income groups including public servants. Weak and illegal financial system leads to result lower growth rate of stock market.

4.11. Monetary and Fiscal policies

1. Monetary Policy Framework

Monitory policy affects interest rate and inflation. Evidence sighted in NBE (2009) monitory policy framework does support the overall the need of establishing secondary market for the government securities. The framework indicates instruments has been extremely limited in Ethiopia due to underdevelopment of the money market and virtual non- existence of financial market.

According to NBE KII reveal that stock market is significant to use a mix of diversified monetary instruments and effectively way to carry out the monetary management however efficient and strong regulation is mandatory in order to achieve the expected result.

According to policy proceeding paper which is organized by AAAC, Ethio-Chamber Business after Hours at Sheraton Addis, February 11, (2019), the agenda of stock market discussion document stated that: stock market provides a number of benefits to borrowers and investors. This includes governments for risk sharing and efficient allocation of capital sake. In addition, the benefit and contribution of stock market for fiscal, monetary, and exchange rate policy is stated as follows.

First, local bond used by the governments to finance large financial deficits without having an option to financial control or foreign borrowing. In reality, the drive for the development of local bond markets naturally came from the government to facilitate the financing of large deficits. Financing deficits through financial control by forcing local banks to hold government paper slow down the development of the domestic banking sector and foreign borrowing in hard currency exposes countries to exchange rate risk.

Second, the development of money and bond markets supports the behavior of monetary policy. Bond markets provide instruments needed for the implementation of monetary policy and improve the transmission mechanism of monetary policy. Long term bonds also facilitate sterilization operations by the central bank because sterilization that relies exclusively on short-term instruments tends to drive up short-term interest rates and encourage further inflows into such instruments. Long-term bond markets give valuable information for the behavior of monetary policy, including expectations about macroeconomic developments and reactions to monetary policy changes, and thus help the operation of monetary policy.

Third, the development of stock markets can develop the availability of long term financing, allowing individuals and firms to better manage interest rate and maturity risk associated with long-term investments (such as investments in equipment, machinery, land and buildings) by allowing for a better match between the duration of financial assets and liabilities. This benefit applies foremost to the development of a local bond market and the development of equity markets can also improve firms' access to long-term capital.

Fourth, the development of local capital markets encourages access to long term-

financing. Bond markets can offer local investors, such as retail and institutional investors, a way to borrow or invest in local currency and better manage inflation and exchange rate risk. It also provides a safe alternative investment to local bank deposit and foreign currency markets can make the country less vulnerable to sudden stops and exchange rate shocks. Governments are major sponsors of local bond markets because it allows financing fiscal deficits by borrowing from domestic markets without exchange rate risk.

Fifth, stock markets allow for financial support alongside the development of banking markets, improving the efficiency of capital allocation in the economy. Bond finance provides healthy competition to bank loans and offers relatively cheap financing to large, reputable firms that have the scale and credentials to tap long-term capital markets. Further, the discipline of the stock market will improve the quality and disclosure of information that firms provide to markets and firm performance.

Sixth, If markets opened to foreign investments, thus increase financial integration by attracting foreign capital, which can lower the cost of capital for local firms and individuals and improve risk sharing across countries. It further improves market access and relieves credit constraints on small and medium-sized enterprises. However, the liberalization of financial markets can also result in the migration of trading to international financial sectors, hampering domestic market development. High-quality firms may try to escape local markets, lowering the average quality of local issuances or local listing or disclosure requirements may be relaxed to prevent trading activity from moving abroad, with negative implications for investor protection.

Finally, the development of stock markets can improve financial stability by enhancing the ability of financial institutions to manage risk. Moreover, a more diverse financial system that includes capital markets alongside banking markets tends to be more stable and better able to absorb shocks. Beside stock market might adverse effect, saver may affect by the interest rate intermesh of returning rate either to invest or to spend.

2. Fiscal policy

Stock market expand tax base. To participating in stock market one of the requirements is a certified financial reporting system and includes tax system. Tax law has a powerful effect on the development of stock market either to discourage or motivation to participate in such market. According to the key informant interviewee from NBE:

‘Policy related a challenge includes tax incentives for security market to promote potential participants on stock investment. Under the mobilizing financial resources the fiscal policy has a pivotal role in maintaining macroeconomic stability thus stock market. Besides, well-functioning stock market is a good way to collect taxing for Ethiopian Inland Revenue as a result of certified financial reporting enforcement, promote transparency and well regulated system’.

The experience of Rwanda stock market shows, the government of Rwanda had taken the following policy measures before establishing capital market at 2010. Among, offered tax incentives including income tax exemption; capital gain tax where secondary market transactions in listed securities. Further, corporate income tax which stipulates that newly listed companies in the capital market are taxed for a period of five years at 20 per cent if these companies sell at least 40 per cent of their shares to the public, at 25 per cent if these companies sell at least 30 per cent of their shares to the public and 28 per cent if these companies sell at least 20 per cent of their shares to the public.

3. Inflation

Increase in the general price level of goods and services in an economy over a period of time resulting in a loss in the value of the currency. The expected sign for inflation is negative as high rates of inflation increase the cost of living and a shift of resources from investments to consumption. This leads to a fall in the demand for market instruments and subsequently to a reduction in the volume of stocks traded. This in turn negatively affects the stock market’s performance. This in turn has a positive effect on stock prices which increase the market capitalization of the stock market. As a result, the stock price

decrease and investing on the stock also decrease.

Table 4.2. NBE quarter report, 2018

Particulars	2017/18		2018/19	Percentage point Changes	
	QI	QIV	QI	Annual	Quarterly
1. Savings Deposit Rate 1/					
Minimum	5	7	7	2	-
Maximum	5.75	9	9	3.25	-
Average Saving Rate	5.38	8	8	2.63	-
2. Time Deposits					
Up to 1yr	5.43	8.05	8.06	2.62	0
1-2 years	5.55	8.1	8.1	2.55	0.01
Over 2 yrs.	5.6	8.13	8.15	2.54	0.01
Average Time Dep. Rate (Weighted)	5.53	8.09	8.1	2.57	0.01
3. Demand Deposit (Weighted)	0.04	0.04	0.04	0	0
4. Lending Rate 2/					
Minimum	7.5	7	7	-0.5	-
Maximum	18	20	20	2	-
Average Lending Rate	12.75	13.5	13.5	0.75	-
5. T-bills Rate (Weighted)	1.42	1.39	1.4	-0.02	0.01
6. GERD Bond Yield 3/					
6.1 Maturity within 5 Years	5.5	7.5	7.5	2	-
6.1 Maturity above 5 Years	6	8	8	2	-
7. Headline Inflation (Year-on-year)	10.8	14.7	12	1.16	-2.7
8. Food Inflation (Year-on-year)	13.2	17.9	13.5	0.26	-4.4
9. Core/non-food Inflation (Year-on-year)	8.1	11	10.3	2.24	-0.7

Source: NBE quarter report, 2018

The affirmation data show that inflation rate per year is 12% in 2018/19 and deposit interest rate maximum from 8 to 9%. In addition interest rate from government bond is 8% by the same year. This shows the inflation rate is much higher than the return of the savings account.

*“According to the interviewee from National Bank of Ethiopia argued,
“There is a negative interest rate due to domestic saving and return from*

government bond because the increment of inflation. Beside, both domestic and foreign direct investment currently cannot cover the gap. In line with this, the current situations poor export performance, unfair balance of trade and political instability can be possible factors and inflation increase consumption than saving” (KII, April, 2019).

4.12. Prospect of Ethiopian government commitment

One of the main determinant factors to develop stock market is the existence of government commitment. Ethiopia had stock market in 1960 and this is stated in chapter two of this work. There has been policy proceeding, debates and discussions to established stock market in Ethiopia, However they do not to get permission from the government. Offered reasons were different in terms of appropriate economic development, political issues and ideological which is developmental state model. Currently Government of Ethiopia appears committed to establish the market development. So far, some evidences exist that suggest the willingness of the government. For example according to February 24, 2019 Financial Times publication, PM Abiye Ahmed pointed out that outline policies in country’s shift towards economic liberalization. In the same token, he declared Ethiopia aims to complete a multibillion-dollar privatization of its telecoms sector by the end of this year, followed by a sell-off of stakes in state energy, shipping and sugar companies. The government also plans to launch a domestic stock exchange in 2020, part of a gradual but decisive shift towards economic liberalization in the fast-growing east African country of estimated 105m people.

He said, “My economic model is capitalism,” and emphasized his policies mark break with the previous administration controlling economy “commanding heights” and reinvesting profit in infrastructure, health and education. In addition, the central bank governor has pointed out in his testimony parliament that government is undertaking a study, in contribution with the IMF, to establish a stock market. The key informant interview with NBE also confirmed the commitment to establish stock market. This

indicates that has some level of interest in the establishment of stock market by the government.

The establishment of Accounting and Auditing Board of Ethiopia and the implementation of IFRS in financial sectors and public enterprises is a good start to establish stock market. Availability of potential listing companies those have law and regulation , international financial and Reporting standard /IFRS/ implementers and have corporate governance , such as banks, insurance and public enterprises are prospects. Another important issue is availability of Proclamation of Public Private Partnership (PPP) is a favorable framework to promote privately financed sector projects. According to Ethiopian PPP proclamation No.(1076-2018), the government contractual with the private sector, through concession or partnership agreement based. Beside, is to build owned or operate projects. To sum up, the government may contribute by different perspective such as by international through debts and stock market to cover their financial need to develop PPP.

Those with limited or no access but can generate adequate revenue to meet their requirement and capability of borrowing capital without direct government help, Individual government and borrow as part of their large group.

All the respondents from the above mentioned respected organizations have something in common they agree the establishment of stock market in Ethiopia but disagreement with the time frame. In spite of strong believes in the establishment, the expected time frame which is stated by the respondents very different each others. Some respondents argued it can established during a short period of time and other expect at least four and above years. Respondents from NBE and AABE argued a minimum of five year is required to establish stock market. On the other hand respondents from AACCC replied it is the right time to establish stock market particularly in Addis Ababa.

CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY OF FINDINGS and RECOMMENDATIONS

Stock market is an integral part of financial system. It helps to mobilize long term capital efficiency by attracting resources from a large number of savers in a cost-efficient manner and by converting the funds of short-term investors into long-term capital. Establishing a stock market will contribute nation regenerate the existing fragmented and uncoordinated share market to a higher level of organization and sophistication. If implemented carefully and with the necessary cautions, a stock market can attract capital and create jobs by reducing the cost of borrowing, igniting investment and economic growth of the country as well as tapping into global equity markets. This research try to assess institutional, macroeconomic and policy issues limiting its establishment and related challenges and prospects in Ethiopia. Accordingly based on the research questions the major findings are stated below.

5.1. Summary of Findings

1. Why stock market not yet established in Ethiopian and what are challenges still exist?

Ethiopia had stock market during Imperial era in 1960s. However, during the Derg regime due to command economic policy every economic activity was fall down to central government and which prohibited free market economy. After 1991, even though there are amendments and reforms in regarding economic policy, financial liberalization still under the question. Stock market is one form of financial liberalization. It is complex, multifaceted and strongly controlled investment. To establish stock market many factors should assessed and considered. In this research some basic factors institutional, macroeconomics and policy are tried to assess.

Institutional factors

- **Policy, Law and regulation:** Stock market needs a remarkable policy, law and standards regulation. In order to develop investor's private sector confidence, an infrastructure investment financing that supports the nation by strategic sectors

of the economy. Stock market flourishes relatively easily macroeconomic and supportive policies, which is solid legal and institutional frameworks. Prime Minister interview with financial times and agenda paper for roadmap shows intention of having 2020 Ethiopia have capital market. However, these researches assert nothing is concrete but only a good start. So, a wide range of reform is anticipated to work. Stock market proclamation, property rights, bankruptcy procedures and competition laws are critical for stock market establishment in order to implement legal and governing structure.

➤ **Regulatory Institution:** Stock market requires institution that independent regulates and supervises the market operation similar to Ethiopia Commodity Exchange (ECX). Regulatory framework and investment law to create a fertile ground for local capital market development. The public body regulatory organization is responsible to control not only every activity but also responsible providing license to those stock market participants as other countries has been did. Until the end of this study, there is no tangible information or data about the establishment of regulatory organization. Well functioning stock mark require supervisory and monitoring capabilities would.

➤ **Central Depository and Investment Banks**

Market Structure: is appropriately line up with central depository system, clearing and trading system of stock market. Central depository system or institutions establish to properly facilitate the trade, payment, clearance and settlement system.

➤ **Accounting and Auditing Standard:** structural reforms are mandatory in areas of financial reporting in order to having a well functioning stock market. The research found that a good start the establishment of Accounting and Auditing Board of Ethiopia (AABE) to regulate the profession. The Board and recognition of international reporting standards for wider use in Ethiopia are in the right direction and the implementation of International Financing and Reporting Standard/IFRs/ in financial institute and mega public enterprises. However, the reviewing is not started yet. Beside there is a capacity and professional expertise to refine and review supplied reported from the first phase stockholders.

- **Corporate governance:** Good corporate governance helps to ensure that the corporate board is accountable to the company, the shareholders and other stockholders to attract more equity capital. So, improving discourse and corporate governance is critical to improving the efficient use of corporate resource. The finding shows that financial institutes and few public enterprises relatively have a good corporate governance system.
- **Infrastructural Development**
Stock market requires adequate market infrastructure. For example asymmetry of information in the stock market is undermining the integrity of the market. Online transaction and clearing system is determinant factor for stock market. Ethiopian telecommunications the only provider of internet based trade under our country context. Thus, it is difficult to get fixed and regular supply of internet technology. However, ECX can be a good example. ECX's marketing system heavily incorporate with Ethio-telecom, thus not prevent to manipulate tasks.
- **Professional**
Professional qualifications are commonly required for stock dealers, brokers, accountants, lawyers, economists, financial analysts and so on, who are main stockholder and key actors under stock market trading. It was difficult to get the concrete data which shows the potential professionals.

2. Is the current economic structure and level development sufficient to initiate a functioning stock market?

Macroeconomic factors

- Economic size, structure, level of development, and prospects are highly correlated with stock market to establish stock market. However, the finding shows that the existing economic growth is positive and enough to establish stock market but with limitation. Threats with such issues of listing companies, illiquidity of secondary market, and market manipulation can be occur. Ethiopian economic size, structure, level and level of development is not as such far away relatively from other east African countries those established stock market. From example: Rwanda, Kenya, and Uganda.

Policy factors

- A well-developed stock market can also serve as a tool for monetary and fiscal policy management. At the beginning stage to encourage market participants' interest rate and taxation policy should be revised. For example Rwanda Government provides fiscal incentives for listing. This includes zero per cent capital gains tax and five per cent dividends tax.

3.What is the prospect for the establishment strong and well-functioning vibrant stock market in Ethiopia in the near future?

- The central bank governor parliamentary testimony shows that government is undertaking a study, in contribution with the IMF, to establish a stock market. The key informant interview with NBE also confirmed the commitment to establish stock market. Prime Minister Abiy Ahmed press releases to financial times also bear out government plans to launch a domestic stock exchange in 2020.
- The decision to partially privatize some of the nation's most prominent assets like Ethiopian Airlines, Ethio telecom, Ethiopian Shipping & Logistics Services Enterprise and the Ethiopian Electric Power Corporation may a good potential suppliers of both primary and secondary market stocks. Further, a well regulated financial institutions such as banks, and micro finances may have a potential to participate the established stock market. However, many private sectors are not enough capacity to incorporate with stock market. Especially their financial reporting standards not enough to say capable to participate stock market but a very good start. The data which is collected from AABE shows some of them are forced to implement IFRS by AABE. But not reviewed yet. Public-Private-Partnership (PPP) framework is expected to alter the way to conduct a favorable business environment to increasing private sector participation include development of Industrial Parks. Thus, it can be good indicator and good prospect source of stock market.

5.2. Recommendations

- Institutions can only be improved slowly after establishment. Hence, it is extremely important for policymakers to know which institutional factors are critical for financial sector development. Legal policy and framework, issue of regulatory body, and issue of corporate governance should carefully considered. During early stage of ECX establishment the following problems were happened. Participants were small farmers and small traders, beside weak infrastructure and disorganized informal markets. Further, weak technology applied to the market gave small actors around this large country an almost inconceivable degree of information and market access. Issue of equal delegation (composed of private and public sector participants), weaker Internet penetration, and a physical trading floor in Addis Ababa. However, they (the first committee of ECX) visit other courtiers' experience and developed a model tailored to Ethiopia's need. In addition, experienced Ethiopian diasporas' can play critical role in both financially and professional expertise. Legal framework and policy should be carefully studied.
- It is also strongly advisable to establish Capital Market Advisory Council and Stock Exchange Market Commission (regulatory Authority) which is behalf of public body starting from the beginning stage as shown by other counties experience.
- Similarly, Ethiopia's focus on the light stock market through the private sector development by providing important effort both to attract foreign investment and domestic private sectors. Studies confirmed that strong correlation between private sector development and stock market.
- Empowering institutions like Accounting and Auditing Board (ABBE), and strengthening Public –Private -Partnerships, is strongly advisable and as well as a good start in order to prevail stock market.
- Confirming political and economic stability of the country is a key factor to any contrary including stock market. Stock market is a type of policy which usually implemented if the country in a good mood.

- Economic prospect it is good to see from international indicators point of view such as IMF and World Bank. But currently difficulty to get data and a full-fledged analysis regarding whether there is GTP III or another strategic plan. But based interview, parliamentary testimony and some media publication. A good strategic plan should be prepared to which appropriately implementing the future regarding the development of stock market.
- Given that comparative advantage tax system to be built with a long term vision and plan at the initial stage of Stock market prevailing.
- Besides, Stock market requires more advanced technology and lay the foundation for accumulation technological infrastructure.
- Policy preference is the first element of the institutional arrangement to apprehend a pre-determined target. Accordingly, it is strongly advisable to give due emphasis to institutional factors, macroeconomic and policy factors which is focusing on the legal issues, economic structure and development issue, monetary and fiscal policies.
- The key lesson from African countries including Rwanda, is that it is essential for Ethiopia to have a clear policy and strategy on the key patterns of stock market establishment from initial public offering(IPO) as the government of Rwanda has been did. Realizing these benefits can ensure accelerated and sustained economic growth that enables to achieve stock market in the economy and increased national incomes. However, this requires carefully prioritizing and selecting determinant factors and policy incentives.
- Opportunities from a well regulated sectors such as banks, insurance, mega public enterprises, and can easily utilize at beginning stage. They can play crucial role to establish as a pilot model. It is advisable establish a useful links between, private sector, public enterprises, public body and academia to develop the market. Currently there are 19 commercial banks and 35 microfinance institutions.
- Policy incentives can also play crucial roles in promoting stock market investment to attract both foreign and domestic investors. In this regard, the lesson from Rwanda shows that policy incentives capital gain tax where

secondary market transactions in listed securities. Accordingly, policy incentive is strongly recommended especially the beginning stage of stock market.

- Knowledge and awareness: Stock market is a knowledge intensive investment sector. Require availability of easily trainable skilled manpower by providing suitable. Accordingly, training, creating awareness and developing skill is mandatory. Learning from those who have experience it is more important. Thus, it is strongly advisable to establish a separate or potential institution that provides build capacity through appropriate training. Using Diasporas knowledge and experience can be key solution. Lesson from Rwanda shows that stock exchange conducted public education sessions in different public and private organizations through seminars, meetings presentations (both domestic and international), radios and TV talks. Training on higher learning Institutions and Universities in Rwanda and abroad are main centers of education and awareness to the majority. Further, learn from the existing international practices.
- Create alliance with a well experienced international academic and financial institute. Stock market requires and promotes effective knowledge, appropriate skill, competence, coordination the effort of different stockholders but limited
- Like other trade and investment stock market require advertisement and promotion especially at early stage of its establishment. One of stock market feature is having strong competition and challenge from media and medium of communication. Thus, stock market establishment in Ethiopia should be supported by proactive promotional strategy so as to attract stock market actors. Organized and professional media is main sources of information to attract investors and active participants. Thus, it is strongly advisable to establish a separate institution that provides evidence based information, promotion and advertisement which is specifically organized for this purpose. Further, to make sure evidence based investment decision making and to develop investors confidence.

In conclusion, I have a strong recommendations that if the government realistic commitment to establish stock market, the aforementioned tasks should be addressed. They are strong foundations and can establish a full-fledged concrete stock exchange market. of course these cannot completed within few years. Beside, stock market is risky and complex investment. Lesson from Rwanda shows: low domestic saving and tax regime, absence of financial intermediaries, lack of adequate accounting and auditing systems, family owned companies and lack of information are incorporated with RSM. If other thing being equal (the above minimum requirements fulfill) It recommended starting in Addis Ababa as a pilot like ECX did at beginning stage and can grown up other

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Appendix's